

Deliverable Task 4.3.8
Thematic Focus Analysis of the Role of
Industry Innovators

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About RRING

The overall project aim is to bring Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) into the linked up global world to promote mutual learning and collaboration in RRI. This will be achieved by the formation of the global RRING community network and by the development and mobilization of a global Open Access RRI knowledge base. RRING will align RRI to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a global common denominator.

The RRING project acknowledges that each region of the world is advancing its own agenda on RRI. Therefore, RRING will not be producing a Global RRI framework or strategy that is meant to be enforced in a top-down manner. Rather, increased coherence and convergence will be achieved via a bottom-up approach, learning from best practices in RRI globally and from linkages, via the new RRING community, to develop the RRI linked-up world.

Six Objectives of RRING

Objective 1: Promote a linked up global world of RRI by creating the global RRING community network, thereby enabling mutual learning, collaboration, mobilization of RRI concepts.

Objective 2: Mobilize, promote and disseminate a global open access knowledge base of RRI based on the State of the Art (SoA) and comparative analysis across the key geographies, all stakeholders and sectors. It will cover key platforms, spaces and players, role and influence of stakeholders, drivers and policies for R&I, regulation in public, private sectors and nation states and international organizations.

Objective 3: Align RRI to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to provide a global common denominator for advancement of RRI and address Grand Challenges globally.

Objective 4: Determine the competitive advantages of RRI and also understand how and where RRI is perceived as a barrier and/ or disadvantage.

Objective 5: Create high level RRI strategy recommendations for the seven geographic zones, trial RRI best practice learning in 2 EU case studies.

Objective 6: Promote inclusive engagement of civil society and researchers.

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Glossary

AIRR: Anticipation, inclusion, reflexivity, responsiveness refers to a process of designing research and innovation which provides a different way of looking at RRI that is not bound by the key pillars but are also part of RRI.

Geographies: the globe will be divided into five major regions (however imperfect this is). The list of countries in each region is found in a Working Document called 'Definition of 5 Geographies' (in the MS Teams folder) that will be annexed in the final version of this report.

Impact: has its plain language meaning, except that it is exclusively a caused measurable event that is to be considered the impact of the application of an RRI aspect, meaning that (an) event(s) that are aspect(s) of RRI caused the measurable event we call an 'impact' (even if the relationship is not or is not known to be deterministic causality).

Key players, key leaders, key networks and key platforms: In general, the ability to achieve sustainable (long-term, qualitative) change, social legitimacy, i.e. the perception of relevant audiences that a player/leader/network/platform promotes change on behalf of either the achievement of the SDGs or the advancement of RRI. Like for 'Stakeholders' a typology will be collectively defined. This will appear in the working document called 'Key Players, Key Leaders, Key Networks and Key Platforms Defined for 4.5' found in MS Teams and will be annexed in a final version of the present report.

Limitation: a basket term including 'barrier' or 'obstacle' or both (all using plain language definitions), is for Task 4.5 an assignment of value applied after a finding that the SDG target has no resonance for the research subject. (This is given its sense in terms of social intervention proposals that might follow, framed by the RRING project's overarching aim to advance RRI, both key pillars and AIRR dimensions, in practice).

Opportunity: will have its plain language meaning, and for Task 4.5, it is an assignment of value designating a finding that a research subject linked an RRI aspect (novel or not) to existing efforts/initiatives that do/aim to achieve any SDG target. (This is given its sense in terms of social intervention proposals that might follow, framed by the RRING project's overarching aim to advance RRI, both key pillars and AIRR dimension, in practice).

Policy drivers: refer to a) an issue or concern that might drive or push the creation of a public policy designed to rectify that issue or concern' (e.g. Covid-19 outbreaks in stage 2 driving travel restrictions), or b) a framework law or policy that guides public policy.

RRI aspect: means a feature or dimension of responsibility in research and innovation. This definition can easily go beyond (and is not limited to the concepts of) what 'RRI' as a conceptual framework has been defined to mean in the European context. That open-ended definition is necessary and intended for this part of the RRING research which examines countries outside of Europe that necessarily use other concepts. An RRI aspect might be materialized by an initiative involving any sort of event(s) (e.g. a new policy, a new tool, etc.) or it might be made evident by a perspective expressed, that 1) aims at advancing responsibility in research and innovation (whether to do with key pillars or AIRR dimensions or not), 2) could be replicated, and 3) already engages more than one person. Novelty is only in terms of being distinguishable from RRI in European context, and each novel RRI aspect identified should be logged in the working document 'Novel RRI aspects', found in MS Teams. This list will appear as an annex in the final version of the present report.

Responsible research and innovation (RRI): An approach to research and innovation that anticipates and assesses potential implications and societal expectations with regard to research and innovation, with the aim to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation.¹ The key pillars of RRI are gender equality, science education, public engagement, open access, ethics and governance.

RRING: Responsible Research and Innovation Networked Globally.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): The 17 goals set out by the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, with 169 targets and 231 unique indicators, which cover social, economic and environmental issues. The goals are all interconnected.

Stakeholder: a common typology is defined collectively (in the working document in MS Teams called 'Stakeholders Defined for T4.5') and this typology or list will be annexed in the final version of the present report. In lower case, the word will have a plain language meaning (a dictionary meaning).

Strategy: has a plain language meaning, and a strategy will be proposed to address each opportunity and limitation identified, with the overall aim of promoting/advancing RRI including its AIRR dimensions. Each strategy is meant to include the following: specific objectives, context, initial plan of actions in a timeline, stakeholders, assessment of consequences/interactions, precedents/comparables, specification of players, leaders, networks and platforms; it may also include identification of public policy interactions, focus areas, and terminology as relevant; and both a short- and medium-term horizon.

United Nations (UN): The international organization with 193 member states that is responsible for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development: Resolution adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015 which lays out global development until 2030. The 2030 Agenda requires a wholistic approach, rather than the North-South approach of the previous Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

1. T4.3.8: Thematic Focus Analysis of the Role of Industry Innovators

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1.1. Executive Summary

The present document examines data from WP3 and WP5. It is divided in three parts: understandings, drivers and challenges of RRI (or RRI-related) ideas in industry innovation, related to the key domains of RRING and the five geographic areas of the UN regional commissions. The three parts of the report analyse data gathered from interviews with industry innovators in the ICT, energy, bioeconomy and waste management areas. Part 1 examines how corporate leaders, staff and researchers understand responsibility and responsible innovation in industry innovation and how they perceive the role and value of RRI in the private sector. Part 2 investigates the drivers for the adoption of RRI aspects in industry. A distinction is made between external and internal drivers as well as moral and instrumental drivers. Part 3 analyses the challenges to the implementation of RRI-related aspects in industry. This includes (i) a discussion of the frictions between RRI ideas as promoted in the public research sector and the characteristics and needs of industry innovation, and (ii) the analysis of social and political factors that influence the ways in which RRI in industry is perceived and adopted in different geographic contexts around the world. The report concludes that formal knowledge of RRI principles, as defined in European policy frameworks, is limited among industry innovators around the world. However, many of our research participants reported of practices that were similar to RRI aspects, or that added important dimensions which in this way do not exist in European RRI discourse. These findings notwithstanding, the report also reveals important problems to and limitations of the adoption of RRI-like ideas in private sector innovation.

1.2. Introduction

Sub-task 4.3.8 is part of Task 4.3. of RRING Work Package 4, that aimed to “Determine best practice from the 5 UNESCO world regions, 4 key domains and the key stakeholder types”. It synthesizes data from WP3 and WP5, that were collected from research participants in Sub-Sahara Africa, Asia, Latin America, the Middle East and Europe and Northern America.

The central aim of sub-task 4.3.8 “Thematic Focus Analysis of the Role of Industry Innovators” was to conduct an analysis of the ways in which industry leaders, staff and researchers in different regions of the world understand, evaluate and use RRI-related (or similar) practices. It also aimed to identify the economic, social and policy drivers for the implementation of RRI aspects in industry, the opportunities and limitations of existing practices, and the barriers to the adoption of RRI (or RRI-like) ideas in private sector settings around the world.

The vast majority of publications that have examined the opportunities, adoption and limitations of RRI in industry, have focused on developments in Europe and the USA. In this deliverable, we provide more diverse, global understandings of how RRI-related aspects are defined, operationalized and used in private sector innovation.

The analytical focus in this report is mainly on perceptions and developments in Africa, Asia, the Middle East and Latin America and we use these insights to discuss commonalities and differences with European and North American conceptions and practices of RRI. The empirical findings in this deliverable are discussed in relation to relevant social science literature. In this way, it contributes to the ongoing academic debate on role, feasibility and challenges of RRI in industry from a global and comparative perspective.

2. Methods

Interview selection

This report is based on the qualitative analysis of interviews with industry innovators that were conducted in 2019 in WP3 and WP5 of the RRING. These work packages conducted a total of 169 interviews (141 from WP 3 and 28 from WP5) with a varied group of stakeholders, that included academic researchers, people from civil societal organizations, public funding agencies, and industry innovators. In a first step we reviewed the body of interview data to identify interviews with industry innovators. Because the main aim

of this report is to examine the situated perceptions of industry innovators, and to understand how this group views the role, possibilities and challenges of RRI in corporate settings, we reviewed the body of interview data to identify interviews with professionals working for industry and the private sector. We included all interviews that were conducted with researchers, R&D managers, CEOs and other staff working for enterprises that involved start-up firms, small to mid-size enterprises, as well as large companies including multi-national corporations. Altogether, 44 interviews from six geographic regions were selected: 13 interviews were from Africa, 4 from Asia, 16 from Europe, 8 from Latin America, 1 from the Middle East, and 2 from North America (see Table 1).

Table 1: Participants from different countries per geographic region

Africa	7 Malawi, 5 Morocco, 1 South Africa
Asia	2 India, 2 Japan
Europe	4 UK, 3 Italy, 3 Serbia, 2 Lithuania, 1 Spain, 1 Germany, 1 Ireland
Latin America	3 Guatemala, 2 Brazil, 1 Bolivia, 1 Colombia, 1 Uruguay
Middle East	1 Egypt
North America	2 USA

Of the 44 interviews, 9 were conducted with industry innovators from the bioeconomy sector, 11 from the energy sector, 17 from the ICT sector, and 7 from the waste sector. The gender ratio of all interviews was 31 male participants versus 13 female participants (see Table 2).

Table 2: Gender ratio and industry sector per geographic region

	Africa	Asia	Europe	Latin America	Middle East	North America
Number of Interviews	13	4	16	8	1	2
Gender ratio: male/female	11 / 2	4 / -	10 / 6	3 / 5	1 / -	2 / -
Energy sector	5	2	2	2	-	-
ICT sector	4	2	7	3	-	1
Bioeconomy sector	1	-	7	1	-	-
Waste management	3	-	-	2	1	1

Coding of the interview data

In order to identify analytically significant features in the data, we developed a coding framework (code book) that was organised around six overarching analytical themes, which were derived deductively from a review of the literature on RRI in industry settings (see Section 3 below). These themes included: understandings of RRI in industry; dimensions and described practices of RRI in industry contexts; perceptions of the role and value of RRI ideas in industry settings; drivers for RRI in industry innovation; challenges to RRI adoption in industry; and challenges to RRI adoption in a diverse global environment.

With one exception, the codes to these overarching analytical themes were then developed inductively, in order to capture participants' assumptions, key insights and the multiple meanings inherent in the text. This involved the close reading of a subsample of 10 of the identified 44 interviews. Only the codes for the theme "dimensions and described practices of RRI in industry" were derived deductively. Here we used the key aspects of the RRI KEYS and AREA frameworks (anticipation, reflexivity, engagement, gender, diversity, inclusion, access to innovation, ethics, etcetera) as analytical instruments, to understand which of these aspects industry innovators prioritize and use in practice. Each code was accompanied by code definitions and sample text segments. The code book was reviewed by RRING partners at the University of

Wageningen and Vilnius University. Suggestions for improvements resulted in a re-reading of some of the interviews.²

The coding frame was then applied systematically to the interview data. In a first cycle of coding the codes in the code book were refined, and additional codes were added (Saldana 2012). Analytically relevant content was labelled, and initial analytical ideas and themes that emerged from the data were identified. After the code book was revised, and first hypotheses about connections between different themes and sub-themes had emerged, a second cycle of coding was conducted. In the second cycle, we re-evaluated and refined the previously attached codes, and added new codes (and corresponding memos) that helped us to identify indications of patterns and themes, that we examined further after the coding of all data was completed. After all interviews were coded, the coded information was organised under analytical categories and themes, in order to understand connections, explain similarities and differences, and to interpret the data in relation to relevant theory.

Methodological limitations:

Due to the relatively small number of interviews with industry innovators, and the unequal distribution of interviews across geographic regions, we were not able to conduct a systematic comparison between the five geographies of the RRING project, and to make further analytical subdivisions from within these regions along the four technology fields. As Table 2 above shows, 16 interviews were conducted with respondents in Europe, 13 in Africa, 8 in Latin America, 4 in Asia, 2 in North America and 1 in the Middle East. This means that the interviews from Europe, Africa and Latin America are higher represented than interviews from Asia, North America and the Middle East. For this reason, we focus mainly on comparisons between data from Europe as well as Africa and Latin America, and draw on data from Asia, the Middle East and North America to contribute to the discussion when relevant. 15 of the 16 European countries (Serbia is the only exception) classify according to data from the World Bank as high-income countries, while most of the African, Latin American and Asian countries included in the sample classify either as upper or lower middle income countries, with Malawi the only country that classifies as low income countries (See Table 3 below).

Table 3: Country Classifications by income (based on 2019 World Bank Classifications)

High-income countries	Asia: Japan Europe: Germany, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Spain, UK Latin America: Uruguay North America: USA	
Upper-Middle Income countries	Africa: South Africa, Europe: Serbia Latin America: Brazil, Colombia, , Guatemala	
Lower-Middle-Income Countries	Africa: Morocco Asia: India Latin America: Bolivia Middle East: Egypt	
Low Income Countries	Africa: Malawi	

² Other 4.3. Teams used inter-coder reliability checks as part of the coding process. We decided that due to the smaller number of interviews with industry stakeholders, inter-coder reliability checks were not necessary. justified and that the review of the codes and code book by our colleagues at the Universities of Wageningen and Vilnius would suffice to ensure the consistent coding of the data.

Europe is also the global region in which most of the (at least early) discourse on RRI was developed and promoted by public funding and other government bodies. Moreover, as the Literature Review in Section 3 below shows, most of the social science literature that examines the adoption of RRI ideas in private sector innovation, focuses on developments in and examples from Europe. This means that, even though a systematic comparison between all the global regions in which interviews were conducted is not possible, the available data allow for a comparative analysis of RRI in industry in high-income countries (in this report mainly from Europe) as well as middle-income countries in Africa, Latin America, Asia and the Middle East. This is the approach that we have taken in this report. Perceptions of RRI among industry stakeholders in Europe are contrasted with the ideas and views on RRI in other world regions, especially from Latin America and Africa, where the majority of our data comes from.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Understandings of Responsible Innovation in Industry

The origins of RRI in Europe and the USA lie primarily in academia and the publicly funded research sector (See Von Schomburg 2019, for an overview and history of RRI in these regions). Yet recent research has begun to consider the potential role and possibilities of RRI principles for firms and industry innovation (Scholten and Blok 2015; Schroeder and Iatridis 2016; Paredes-Frigolett 2016; Stahl 2017; Martinuzzi et al 2018; Blok, Scholten and Long 2019). While there is a long-standing academic interest into the responsibilities of corporations towards society and the environment (for an overview see Lubberink 2017), a specific concern with the possible contribution of RRI in industry has emerged only in the last 4-5 years (Blok and Lemmens, 2015).

Various studies have indicated that awareness of RRI and RRI-like ideas is limited among private sector innovators and only gradually emerging. Based on workshops conducted in seven European countries, as well as Australia, Brazil, China, India and the USA, Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg (2018) report that many corporate leaders and other stakeholders had no prior knowledge of the term. These authors report, that the majority of participants from this study ‘framed RRI intuitively, from their personal experiences and world views (e.g. in terms of research integrity), or to align it to a dominant discourse within their organizations (e.g. CSR for industry)’ (Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg 2018: 3). Auer and Jarmai (2018), in a study of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the medical devices sector in Austria, also conclude that employees in these firms were largely unaware of the RRI concept. Similar findings have been reported in other studies (Blok and Lemmens 2015; Davies and Horst 2015; Stahl 2018; Jarmai 2020).

A characteristic of many of these studies is, that they have evaluated industry perceptions of European RRI frameworks (such as AIRR or RRI Keys), and to what extent understandings and practices in firms conform to these principles. For example, Chatfield and colleagues (2017a), in a study of the European ICT sector, infer that the management approach in most European companies is ‘not currently aligned with RRI values’. They conclude, that while managers and staff in these companies were generally open to the ideas and principles of responsible innovation, at a practical level the concept of RRI was new to most participants in this study, and the integration of RRI principles into management decisions was not yet existent.

In this report, and the RRING project more generally, we take a more open, explorative approach that tries to capture the core ethos of RRI, while allowing to examine understandings, drivers and policies that are possibly only loosely related to the core characteristics of RRI, in the sense that they aim to make research and innovation more sustainable, inclusive and sensitive to societal concerns and expectations.

3.2. Drivers of Responsible Innovation in Industry

The adoption of RRI has the potential to change industry innovation in several ways. With its emphasis on reflection, public engagement and the anticipation of long-term societal and environmental consequences, RRI seeks to restructure existing innovation practices and to achieve greater alignment with societal needs

and problems. These changes require new types of labor and resources, but do not necessarily translate into financial profits (Martinuzzi et al. 2018). Moreover, in some cases, RRI adoption is likely to prevent exploitation of a profitable product (or service or technology), for example when it is considered to create problematic environmental or societal effects. But what are the drivers for the adoption of RRI in private sector innovation? What are possible incentives and what can industry innovators gain from engaging with RRI principles?

3.2.1. External Drivers

Several publications have examined the external drivers that may lead to RRI integration, which arise from the outward context in which private sector innovation takes place. External drivers, as Schoenherr, Martinuzzi and Jarmai (2019) have stressed, include factors such as regulatory and legal frameworks, professional standards (such as PAS440, the recently introduced Responsible Innovation Guide for corporations in the UK), and the promotion of RI criteria by funding bodies and other financing requirements. Auer and Jarmai (2018) have pointed to other factors, which include pressures to respond to the expectations of consumers and civil society, and the need to comply with specific rules or codes of conduct in the context of collaborations (for example with academic partners, and/or companies, stakeholders and users in other countries). Schroeder (2020), in turn, has highlighted the role of institutional policies within firms or sectors and whether these promote principles such as gender equality, diversity or eco-friendly innovation. These factors, as Schoenherr, Martinuzzi and Jarmai (2019) have argued, are intrinsically linked to the political priorities as well as ethical and belief systems that exist in specific regions, communities and countries.

3.2.2. Internal Drivers

Internal drivers, on the other hand, refer to factors that arise within firms and that act as catalysts in favour of the adoption of RRI principles. Several studies have suggested that RRI can help companies to develop new links with customers, in order to understand public perceptions and to identify innovation challenges at an early stage (Stahl 2018; Schroeder 2020; Flick, Fisk and Ogoh 2020). Others have stressed the benefits of engagement with experts, policy makers and politicians, to facilitate alignment with regulatory expectations and to obtain broad public support (Bessant and Iakovleva 2019; Divella and Sterlacchini 2019). According to Schroeder (2020), these forms of engagement help companies to gain a competitive edge and to avoid the development of products that the market will not accept. Lees and Lees (2018), in a case study of New Zealand's sheep diary industry, state that responsiveness to consumer needs can also help to foster competitiveness of products that are destined for distant markets. These authors suggest, that RRI integration (realized in this case through the development of more ethical supply chains) can serve as a differentiation strategy from other markets, that increases consumer trust and warrants the continued sale of products (Lees and Lees 2018; Blok Scholten and Long 2018; Ko and Kim 2020). However, as Dalziel et al. (2018) argue, the outcomes of aligning the business operations of firms with public values depend largely on customer preferences, which vary across and also within countries. In some cases, the costs associated with RRI may not result in increased value or make products less attractive, for example because customers are not willing to pay the added costs of more ethical or responsible production and distribution.

Schoenherr, Martinuzzi and Jarmai (2020) point to another internal driver that is essential for RRI adoption in firms: the motivations and moral standards of corporate decision makers and staff, and the extent to which they are willing to integrate these values in the development of ethical and sustainable products, services and supply chains. Ultimately, these authors argue, innovative firms, have to 'decide for themselves what they consider as their responsibility towards society, and how much this decision is based on success measured in economic terms' (Schoenherr, Martinuzzi and Jarmai 2020: 88).

3.2.3. Moral versus instrumental Drivers

A central theme in existing publications on RRI in the private sector is whether corporations adopt RRI for instrumental motives, such as the generation of new profits or to legitimize controversial products, or for the realization of a broader social good. Garst and colleagues (2017) introduce in this respect a distinction

between instrumental and moral motives to RRI adoption. Based on empirical research in eight food firms in the Netherlands, this study finds that moral motives (such as a commitment to healthy eating, not to mislead customers and to use ingredients from trustworthy supplies) were seen as essential for firm survival and closely intertwined with instrumental motives such as fulfilling consumer demands, staying competitive and managing firm reputation. Garst and her co-authors suggest, however, that it would be reductionist to understand the prominent role of instrumental motives in RRI adoption as merely serving a firm's self-interest. Instead, they conclude, the adoption of instrumental motives is a fundamental prerequisite in the realization of responsible innovation in the private sector. The adoption of instrumental motives, from this perspective, plays a central role in the development and dissemination of responsible products (Garst et al. 2017).

3.3. Challenges to the Adoption of Responsible Innovation in Industry

3.3.1. Frictions between public sector and industry RRI

A central issue that affects the implementation of RRI ideas in private sector innovation, is that there is a misalignment of existing RRI concepts with current industry practices (Dreyer et al. 2017; Stahl et al. 2019). Not only do current RRI frameworks not distinguish between research, development and commercialization, but they also neglect to take into account the specific characteristics of innovation processes in industry (Lubberink et al. 2017). This creates important challenges for the adoption and implementation of RI in industry contexts. The literature indicates three central problems that hinder RRI implementation in the private sector.

A first point is a tension between calls for transparency and the need for secrecy in corporate contexts. Van Schomberg (2011) defined responsible innovation as a 'transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other' (2011: 42). While transparency of research procedures, aims and future applications seems often achievable in academic research (Vilanova and Porcar 2014) it is more problematic in industry innovation. As Blok and Lemmens have pointed out, 'the call for transparency of innovation processes is highly naïve' (2015: 23). Innovation is the main source of competitiveness in corporations, and information asymmetries and corresponding forms of secrecy and non-disclosure are crucial elements to secure intellectual property and to maintain a competitive advantage (*ibid.*). This also affects RRI demands for open access publications (Blok, Hoffmans and Wubben 2015).

3.3.2. Political contexts and RRI implementation

Another key aspect that influences the ways in which RRI is understood and implemented are the broader political and socio-economic contexts in which private sector innovation takes place (Scherer and Voegtlin 2020). Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg (2018) have shown that national political and cultural contexts present important macro-frameworks that shape the adoption and use of RRI concepts in important ways. For example, in rapidly developing countries such as China, and India the realization of fast social and economic development is often a key priority, which makes a systematic engagement with the longer-term effects of innovation processes more difficult (Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg 2018; *cf.* Ladikas et al. 2015).

High income countries, in turn, with established democratic traditions of dialogue and deliberation, form according to Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg, a more fertile ground for RRI adoption. But also in wealthy societies such as the UK and the USA, the systematic anticipation of future innovation effects is often insufficiently realized. Moreover, technology assessment takes place in a highly politicized environment. Long and Blok (2017) discuss in this regard how Trumpism, Brexit and wider populism interact with the adoption and implementation of RRI in both, academic and corporate settings. The authors suggest that a more systematic adoption of RRI is clearly threatened by these political developments. They conclude that

in light of recent trends, such as for instance anti-climate science positions propagated by the White House, an engagement with responsible innovation ideas is more important than ever. For this reason, Long and Blok propose that RRI needs to go beyond a method for facilitating social input into research and innovation, and evolve into an approach that enables reliable, independent analysis of (un)desirable future impacts (Long and Blok 2015: 68).

3.3.3. The role of resources in RRI implementation

Financial resources and committed leadership are crucial components for the implementation of RRI. However, the execution of RRI is often hindered by a lack of education, training and resources. Scientists, in both universities and corporations, are often unaware of RRI imperatives, not trained to integrate RRI aspects in their work and may conceive of responsible innovation primarily in terms of (technical) research integrity (Auer and Jarmai 2017; Stahl et al. 2019). Furthermore, the infrastructures and resources for RRI adoption are in many countries insufficient (Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg 2018: 4). However, as Halme and Korpela's (2018) research on RRI adoption in small-to-mid size enterprises (SMEs) indicates, SMEs can create responsible innovation with very different resource combinations. While sufficient financial resources are always a pre-condition, resource needs vary between business and technical innovation. Other studies have shown that in addition to finance, RRI adoption depends also on various forms of social capital, such as existing networks and collaborations with implicated stakeholders and third parties, industry knowledge and also reputation (Timmermans et al. 2017; Ceicyte and Petraite 2018).

4. Results part 1: Understandings of responsible innovation

How do corporate leaders, managers and staff understand and interpret the conceptual framework, principles and objectives of RRI? How do private sector innovators perceive of the role and value of RRI in the context of industry innovation? And how do these perceptions differ between private sector innovators from high and lower income countries?

In the next sections we will address these questions on the basis of the interview data. We will, first, examine how respondents define responsible innovation in the context of industry innovation. We will, then, look at perceptions of the role and value of four RRI dimensions that were explored in the interviews. These are: anticipation of future implications; societal and stakeholder engagement; issues related to gender equality, diversity and inclusion; and the link between innovation and societal needs.

4.1. Definitions of responsible innovation

In the interviews with industry staff, managers and researchers from around the world, respondents expressed a wide range of understandings of what responsible innovation means in the context of their work. Unsurprisingly, several respondents indicated unfamiliarity with European understandings of RRI. However, as we will show in this and the following sections, findings of our interviews from Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Middle East include a broad range of interesting ideas and practices. Many of these bear similarities with aspects of the European RRI discourse. Others divert from European RRI ideas in interesting ways, and add new impulses and ideas, indicating close links with (or directly responding to) the social and political context in which they have emerged.

4.1.1. Honesty and sidestepping illegal activity and corruption

The next sections provide an overview of a cross-range of different understandings of RRI, as put forward in the interviews. Then, in section 4.1.5 we will examine differences in understandings across global regions, and then relate these findings to the existing literature on RRI in industry. A first understanding of RRI that emerged among industry innovators, was to stay away from illegal activities and corruption.

[In our field], we would have benefited a lot from [...] illegal ways, based on lack of knowledge of people in the field and many [possibilities for] manipulations in the calculations, which are possible. So being responsible and honest is a key factor for our sustainability. (Interview Egypt Nr. 10, large firm, waste industry, male).

Working in areas where there are issues of graft and corruption, you have to be concerned about collusion. [This can] favor certain kind of activities and [...] certain trends or certain organizations over others. (Interview USA 06; waste industry; male).

4.1.2. Avoiding harm and misuse of corporate authority

Another interpretation of responsible innovation was to prevent the misuse of corporate authority and harm that could be caused by ruthless corporate behavior. The first respondent, from Serbia, for example state industry innovation should serve a broader goal, defined as public interests, not just the expansion of influence of firms themselves. The second quotation, from a respondent in the UK, leads this point further by saying that reckless innovation can create serious harm, and that innovation decisions can have damaging and irreversible consequences. For this reason, this interviewee stresses, that an understanding of the concerns of citizens, and a deeper understanding of what society thinks is beneficial, is an essential component in industry innovation.

Above all, responsibility [is related] to the role someone has in the world, and towards the fact that when you work on something you are representing some goals, some wider interest, some public interest, some money that is not yours. [...] This is where I see the main responsibility factor, in relation to the way you apply the authority you have. (Interview Serbia O3, ICT industry, male)

[N]ot being reckless; so not doing things that are irreversible and could be damaging. I think there is a responsibility towards the people who are going to be affected by what you are doing, trying to understand what concerns they have, what benefits they might want to seek from what you are doing. I think when we tend to talk about the benefits in the company, we don't often discuss quite how value laden [perceptions of public benefits] are. So, trying to get a much deeper understanding of what society as a whole thinks is beneficial; rather than what we [as a firm] think is beneficial, or what our immediate customer thinks that is beneficial. That is irresponsible. (Interview Great Britain 01, bioeconomy, male)

The next respondent, from Brazil, makes a similar point. He emphasizes the importance to plan innovation processes carefully and to anticipate potential future consequences on society and the environment. According to this respondent, the identification of pathways that connect with societal needs and enable positive forms of future impact, are key aspects of responsible innovation in the private sector.

For me, [responsible innovation] is the combination of several components. Responsible in the sense that those who are involved in the research and handling certain substances that require care from the point of view of self-safety. [T]his is one side of responsibility. And at the other extreme, [are] things like environmental impact, social impact. [The] most important of these components is the look to the future. How does what we do today have a positive impact or not in the future? How does [what happens in] the future mean that we will have a better unity here for a long time? What can we do today? I think this might require a greater stimulus to think of responsibility in research. (Interview Brazil 2, energy sector, male)

4.1.3. Combine profit-making and progress in local communities

Another definition of responsible innovation that came into view in the interviews, was the idea to combine the generation of economic progress with the realization of progress or positive developments in local communities. This idea was especially articulated by respondents in middle income countries in Africa (first quotation, from Morocco) and Asia (second quote, from India), where social disparities are more pronounced than in most high-income countries.

Responsible [innovation] is to set up a set of practices in order to respect the principles of sustainable development, that is to say, to be economically viable, have a positive impact on society but also better respect the environment. (Interview Morocco 1, large firm, energy, male)

Success involves giving back to the society and obviously, only an organization which is sustainable, both economically and ecologically would be able to give back to society. [We] are is very passionate about being innovative in our approach. [Our] focus is, mostly, on [the development of new] ways to wealth. Nothing that [society] uses should be wasted. Because much waste can be converted to wealth, it is [good] for the betterment of society. It also serves as our vision of zero harm, zero discharge. (Interview 5.2.4 India, large company, energy sector, male)

Both of these statements define responsibility in corporate innovation as the need to create a positive impact on society, and to give back to society, while simultaneously allowing for the generation of economic profits. The following quotation makes a similar point, pointing out that social welfare and economic viability must be a key component of responsible innovation in firms. As this respondent (also from India) emphasizes, responsible innovation involves a more holistic approach of economic welfare, where individual firms do not only think their own well-being or survival, but consider the broader network of stakeholders that are involved in, and benefit from, a new innovation. These involve, for example, employees, down-stream industries and vendors, that contribute to or are affected by innovation processes in firms. However, as the quote shows, a sole concern with the economic welfare of these groups is not enough, but must be combined with the realization of sustainable innovation, diversity engagement, and societal development at a more general level.

I would say responsible [innovation] is a very big ambition. Being responsible is not just talking about the environment, talking about safety or diversity for that matter. Responsible development and responsible research or innovation is about, it includes the economic welfare. [...] You have to ensure that the organization is economically feasible. Yeah. So, the people to whom we are providing employment and all the vendors and downstream industries that are associated with us, for all of them, the primary cause of success would be the economic viability of the business. Yeah. So economic viability of business, low emissions, promotion of renewables, societal development and diversity engagement, all these together would form how responsible research or responsible development is played. So, we're trying to juggle all these different [aims]. (Interview India 6, large company, energy sector, male).

4.1.4. Economic value more important than value for society

The quotations in the previous section illustrate that according to several respondents the implementation of RRI-like ideas in firms, is realistic only when it can be combined with economic success. The implementation of RRI-like ideas in firms, as the quotations above illustrates, must be balanced with economic success, which is a pre-requisite for firm survival and employment. However, as the statement below reveals, at least in some firms, the generation of value is ultimately more important than the creation of value for society, which often seems an afterthought.

I have to confess that in general we measure first if [an innovation] creates value for the company, obviously without attacking [doing harm to] society. [...] If we have a great opportunity that creates a lot of value for society, but if for the company it does not create value, then surely, we do not make it. In that we are quite raw. (Interview 5.2.3, Uruguay, energy sector, male)

This quotation conveys that as long as societal benefits can be transformed into profits it is a path worthwhile to pursue. If on the other hand, a new product or service does not make a contribution to society, but is promising in economic terms, many firms will innovate nonetheless.

4.1.5. Intermediary Discussion

Many of the understandings of responsible innovation that industry innovators from Asia, Africa, Latin America and the Middle East expressed in the above sections resonate with European conceptions of RRI. Similar to the academic RRI discourse in Europe (e.g., Van Schomberg 2013; Stilgoe, Owen and Macnaghten 2013), respondents stressed the need to anticipate future impacts, to connect innovation processes with societal needs, understand the concerns of citizens, avoid harm to present and future generations and to realize sustainable forms of innovation that prevent pollution and other forms of environmental damage. Whether these similarities represent the influence of European-originated RRI ideas or reflect locally evolved priorities is not clear, but they convey an awareness that industry innovation can have problematic consequences that should be identified and if possible addressed.

However, there are also important differences from European conceptions of RRI. Demands to stay clear from corruption, collusion and illegal activities, have not been part of the mainstream RRI discourse in high-income countries. Corruption, as we show in Part 6 of this report, has also been mentioned as one of the challenges to facilitate RRI adoption in industry contexts, at least in low and middle income countries. A possible reason is, that RRI in Europe aimed for many years to inform innovation processes in the public research sector, where possibilities for corruption are relatively low and integrity standards are strictly imposed. In industry innovation, on the other hand, where powerful financial incentives can augment the potential for bribery and deception, the meanings of responsibility and responsible innovation change and encompass new dimensions. The fact that graft and corruption was mentioned by a business executive from the USA (in Section 4.1.1. above) illustrates, of course, that dishonest research and business practices, and other unlawful practices are a global phenomenon, that can also be observed in high-income countries (see also Lourenco et al. 2018).

Another difference from main-stream public sector RRI definitions in Europe, are conceptions of RRI that stress the need to combine profit making with the realization of progress and development in local communities (as in Section 4.1.3 above). In the RRING interviews, and also in a recent review of research projects that engage with RRI (and similar) ideas around the world (Rosemann, Jiya and Wakunuma 2020), interpretations of RRI as a means to promote local development were especially pronounced in low and middle income countries, where academic institutions and firms operate in a context of significant social inequalities. While ideas to benefit local communities, and to connect industry innovation to the interests of citizens were also mentioned by respondents from high income countries, the specific link to ideas of social and economic development were especially put forward by respondents from middle income countries that are marked by deep-seated socio-economic inequalities.

Conversely, statements that the implementation of RRI (or RRI-like ideas) is of interest to firms only, if it can be combined with economic success, as expressed by respondents in Section 4.1.3 and 4.1.4. above, resonate strongly with findings from studies on RRI in industry in Europe (Chatfield et al. 2017a; Martinuzzi 2018). The adoption of RRI practices in industry, that do not translate into profits or reputational benefits, these studies suggest, is a dead end.

4.2. Perceptions of the role and value of key RRI dimensions

The following sections look at interviewees' perceptions of the role and value of four RRI dimensions. These are: anticipation of future implications; societal and stakeholder engagement; issues related to gender equality, diversity and inclusion; and the link between innovation and societal needs.

4.2.1 Anticipation

The next sections look at perceptions of the role and value of anticipation and at the forms and understandings of anticipation that industry innovators in different parts of the world articulate and implement. At a more general level, meanings of anticipation varied widely in the interview data. Many respondents were not familiar with the way the concept is used in European RRI discourse and made sense of the term in common sensical terms, or in relation to needs or pressures that arose from their work.

4.2.1.1. Anticipation as a form of business planning

Several respondents made sense of anticipation as a form of organizational planning, with the aim to identify future innovation trends and expand a firm's influence. This is reflected in the following two quotations. The first respondent, who works for a large firm in the ICT sector in Morocco, described the anticipation of future implications as a form of strategic planning that provides new business opportunities.

Interviewer: As you develop your work, how do you take into account the future implications of your work?

I have a plan to do my work because if I don't have a plan, I can't do my work. Sometimes it's not a very good plan and we change it from time to time. [...] So, the future implication of my work it's... maybe we can improve the cluster of technical textiles, because we help [...] startups and people that are involved in [this sector]. (Interview Morocco 6, larger firm, ICT, male).

The second quotation, from a business executive in a large ICT firm in the USA, makes a similar point. From her perspective, anticipation is a way to understand emerging innovation and product trends, and to invest resources to influence these trends and harness their potential:

What we do look at, for example, [is] where technology is moving and whether we can influence where it's going. [...] In our work, we try to pre-empt where things are going, in as much as we can. We try to lead where technology is going, so we make bets, essentially, on if we can see that there is a bifurcation in the road coming, where it will either go towards. I don't know, self-driving cars or flying cars, we would choose one path and say, "That's what where we think it should go. And so that's what we're putting our efforts. (Interview GB 2, large firm, ICT, female).

These understandings differ from the idea of anticipatory governance, as promoted in the RRI frameworks of European funding agencies, which emphasize the importance to anticipate the longer-term societal and environmental implications of new innovations. Many respondents were either unaware or ignored these understandings, and defined anticipation mainly in terms of a firm's strategic goals and business interests.

4.2.1.2. Anticipation as risk management

The findings from the previous section relate loosely to Pavie and Egal's study of RRI in the European ICT sector, which concluded that a concern with the broader and longer-term societal implications of innovation was in many companies absent. According to these authors, many companies de-prioritize a concern with long-term risks and consequences, sometimes on the basis of the argument that their ability to forecast is limited (Pavie and Egal 2014). Some of the respondents in the RRING study, expressed similar perceptions:

I don't think it's possible to really grasp the full breadth of what you're doing in terms of what [an innovation] might enable in the future. It's kind of asking, back in the '60s, "What's the impact computers are going have?" It's similar, right? I mean in wireless, especially, we have no idea what's going to happen 40 years from now with technology we're creating. So we do our best. I think it's a discussion that you can't have once, but fundamentally, you're talking about doing the best you can. There's no closed-form solution to it. (Interview USA 9, large company, ICT sector, male)

This and other quotations imply that many respondents prioritize the anticipation of short and mid-term risks, especially if these threaten to impact on the economic access of an innovation. A concern with longer-term risks, on the other hand, was mostly neglected. While it is true that the accurate prediction of longer-term societal and environmental consequences of new technology developments is difficult, many firms seems to use this argument to prevent longer-term forms of anticipation altogether (c.f. Pavie and Egal 2014; Chatfield et al 2017b).

4.2.1.3. Anticipation of risks to prevent reputational damage

A key finding from another study on RRI in the ICT industry in Europe has shown that even though the assessment and managing of risks is important to firms, many managers perceive of risks primarily in terms of possible adverse effects for companies themselves (Chatfield et al. 2017b). An awareness of the full extent of ethical, societal or environmental risks, these authors state, was often lacking (*ibid.*). Some of the RRING interview data point into a similar direction: many industry innovators use anticipation strategically, to improve a company's reputation, and in this way to contribute to its economic success.

When there is some risk [with partners], [you need] an evaluation of who will be the partner organization, [do they] comply with all aspects of the laws, or the [conditions] in the contract [which] describe that you have to meet the child labor issue, and slave labor. (Interview Brazil 1, large firm, bioeconomy, female).

While the prevention of child and slave labor, the vetting of partner organizations, and compliance with existing legal framework are important aims that, if implemented, reduce unacceptable suffering, identification of these problems is closely linked to the management of short-term reputational risks, not to the management of longer-term risks.

4.2.1.4. Anticipation to identify negative effects on the environment

While the previous paragraphs illustrate that conceptions of anticipation in private sector contexts are often aligned with core business needs, at least some respondents understood the term as a way to identify longer-term negative environmental or societal effects, similar to the European RRI discourse.

Recently we have [looked at the] production chain of cosmetics [and] all ingredients. What are the ingredients that generate the most negative impact? [And] where it is generating negative impact? Which are the ones that generate the most positive impacts, so that people can adopt [those], and seek a transition [away from] those that generate negative impact. Take for example the case of the palm oil. We know that [palm oil tree] monocultures have a negative impact, [...] deforestation, loss of biodiversity. So, for 10 years we have now been studying a new way. To bring more benefits there, and to generate positive impact. (Interview Brazil 1, large company, bioeconomy female).

4.2.1.4. Intermediary Discussion

The findings in the preceding sections indicate that many industry innovators are not familiar with ideas of anticipation as promoted in the European public sector RRI discourse, and do not integrate these in everyday innovation and business practice. As our data, and corresponding evidence from the literature indicates, this applies to both, industry innovators from high and middle income countries, including from the European Union, where the anticipation of the longer-term societal effects of new innovations is actively promoted by public funding bodies.

Instead, anticipation was defined in various alternative ways, that ranged from organizational and business planning, to the identification of new innovation and product trends, to the identification of risks to prevent reputational damage. All of these conceptions were linked to the immediate business needs of firms. While the need to comply, for example, with anti-slavery or child labor legislation forces firms to engage with specific problems, these forms of anticipation relate mostly to production of new products or technologies, they do not take into account the broader and longer-term implications of innovation trends on societies as a whole. While some respondents expressed a concern with environmental sustainability, it was not clear whether and how anticipation was used to identify these issues or inform innovation decision and processes in firms. The amount of data that are available for this report, are insufficient for a comparative geographically informed analysis of industry stakeholders' views on anticipation. In order to identify variation and patterns between geographic regions, industrial sector and also firm size, more research would be required to explore actual anticipation practices among firms in different world regions.

However, the findings in the above sections indicate, that lack of awareness and motivation to explore the longer-term innovation effects from a more holistic perspective, that takes into account perceptions of

shared responsibility and common good, is common in many firms not only in low and middle income countries, where economic resources are likely to be less ample, but also in companies from high income countries.

4.2.2. Engagement

The adoption of RRI and sustainability paradigms in innovation, involves deliberation with multiple societal groups, including laypeople and consumers, employees, civil societal organizations, government and institutional actors (Gurzawska et al. 2017). But how do corporate staff and decision makers perceive and implement stakeholder engagement? And for which purposes do they employ engagement practices?

Blok, Hoffmans and Wubben (2015), in a study of the Dutch food industry, have shown that there are various disincentives for firms to engage with stakeholders. These range from concerns that knowledge disclosed during engagement will leak to competitors, to ideas that differences among stakeholder views create new barriers to innovation, to more practical issues, such as the time and costs required for stakeholder engagement. These authors conclude, that for these and other reasons, many firms are still far from implementing the RRI ideal of mutual responsiveness, transparency and broad stakeholder engagement (Blok, Scholten and Long 2018).

Auer and Jamai's (2017) study of the Austrian medical device sector, on the other hand, illustrates that engagement with diverse stakeholders was common in the sector. However, the aims of engagement were mainly financially: to situate new products in the market and adjust them to the needs and expectations of customers. An ethnographic study on responsible innovation in the finance sector, conducted by Asante and colleagues (2015) reached at similar conclusion. While corporate staff in the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis considered public engagement as crucial to the development of responsible financial innovation, they framed it largely in terms of maintaining public trust and considering client needs.

4.2.2.1. Limited understandings of the concept of public engagement

Our data indicate that, at a more global level, many industry innovators have difficulties to conceptualise the idea of public engagement, as used in European RRI discourse. Several respondents had no clear understanding of the concept of public engagement. Answers to the question, "In engaging the public, how does your work involve individuals or organisations from outside your team and your institution or organization?"³ were often vague, and referred to collaborations with other firms, supply companies, and universities.

[There are] several types of relationships. [...] There are [research] partners [with which we explore a shared] vision of technical cooperation; partners who are related to [us through] the provision of services, [and those we need to] have to develop new equipment. So, it's [...] companies that work together with us. (Interview Brazil 1, mid-size company, bioeconomy, female)

We collaborate with the University, figuratively speaking by default. My company was created out of necessity to make a solid connection and transfer knowledge from science into practice, [so] the fact that collaboration with the University is something that is a must. Not only in terms of gaining knowledge from the University, but my efforts to bring the University a little closer to our everyday life, and that sometimes happens, sometimes not, but that's one thing. (Interview Serbia 4, SME, bioeconomy, female)

³ This was a standardized interview questions for the interviews conducted in Work Package 3.

4.2.2.2. Engagement to understand customer needs and identify new market opportunities

Another meaning that emerged from the data was engagement as a form of customer research, where firms would reach out to customers, to understand their preferences and needs.

Okay. So, may be just to put it into a perspective, we are a solution-based firm. Our main goal is to provide IT solutions to individuals and organisations. So, normally we are attached with the public with the aim of understanding what they are looking for at a certain point time. Or just to appreciate the problems they are facing with regards to IT. From there, that's when we move on to start working on solutions that may probably sort out the issues that they have mentioned at that time. Usually, there is a lot of interaction [...] between us and the public or individuals so that we are able to provide solutions that they are looking for. (Interview 2, Malawi, ICT industry, male)

Others interpreted the idea of public engagement as a way to advertise their products and to create new market opportunities.

We collaborate with educational organizations, especially lately with kindergartens and preschools, because they finally recognized that what we can fully contribute to an educational success with these kids. (Interview Serbia 4, SME, bioeconomy, female)

4.2.2.3. Engagement as a means to change public opinion

A key question is, when and under which circumstances the adoption of public engagement and stakeholder deliberation becomes important, beneficial (or unavoidable) for firms. Asante's et al.'s (2015) research suggests that the more controversial or disruptive a new technology or product is, the more likely that corporations take up stakeholder engagement. Some of the interviews confirm this hypothesis. For many industry innovators, a central aim to engage with the wider public, was to alter public opinions and distrust. A respondent from an international biotech company, for example, that uses genetically modified (GM) organisms to produce agrochemicals and crops, reported the following:

We work with charities, say [a] wildlife charity, [to show that our product] minimized the impact on wildlife [...]. If we do it in this way, it tends to reduce the suspicion of what you are doing. If the wildlife charity says this new mechanism produces benefits rather than we say [this], people will believe it and I think it is extremely helpful to get this sort of 3rd party... trusted 3rd party validation for the claims or your products or processes, rather than making them yourself. (Interview GB 1, large company, bioeconomy, male).

4.2.2.4. Engagement as strategy to influence political and regulatory decisions making

The same respondent also clarified that engagement with stakeholders, such as international NGOs, can have important effects on political and regulatory decision making.

Sometimes we have discussions with environmental charities [...] throughout the world because that can be very influential on political decision-making and then [the] implementation of regulatory decision-making. So you see, they are a very important group of people to talk to. I think anybody who has some influence on how regulations are developed and how regulations are implemented for the sorts of products we are developing; we will be willing to talk to them, and [also] try to understand their problems better. We often get criticisms from NGOs who do not like GM crops or pesticides, or whatever it is. We can try to understand [...] what their concerns are and [we] increasingly are trying to identify common ground. Rather than arguing about what we disagree, we can find something that we agree on and work on that to build stronger relationships. (Interview GB 1, large company, bioeconomy, male).

4.2.2.5. Reading the social environment

The next quotation, from a company manager of a large ICT company in Malawi, illustrates another function of public engagement in the private sector: the ability to understand and read the social environment and value commitments of local communities, and to use this information to realize public support and cooperation in the context of research and other work.

So, firstly it's from the perspective of the [social] environment or the community in which we are working or where we are [...] doing research. What are the social values that they entrench or value? We know that if we go against those - their values - we are not going to get cooperation and we are not going to get what we want. So, we first of all have to factor in those elements. [It] means that we have to do our homework to understand that context and to be able to incorporate the things that they value. That entails that we are working with the people from those particular communities; to get an understanding to say... maybe here language matters, maybe here religion matters, maybe here respect for the local chiefs' matter. All those things. So, we have to understand those and factor them in. (Malawi Interview 5.2.7, large company, ICT-health; male).

4.2.2.6. Engagement as corporate image management

However, the same respondent also clarifies that firm engagement with communities and people at the grassroots, can serve as a strategy for corporate image management. While information on social values and other contextual factors provides important opportunities for learning, engagement activities are documented and shared as examples of best practice via social media and other platforms.

[The] information that we are getting from people in terms of the contextual parameters, social values and different other aspects, we are [using this to] constantly [to] include it in the reports, and share them as lessons or best practices; to think about or to adopt them [to] design a successful system. So, [...] we are interacting with the people, and then we document them and share [this information] in different platforms. For example, in the reports that we compile, in newsletters, in blog posts and also on the social media. We like to [...] grab some of our key moments [when] interacting with communities, and just share it on social media. For us, this connects us to the people, and we feel we are not doing things in isolation or in a vacuum. (interview 5.2.7 Malawi, large company, ICT, male)

4.2.2.6. Intermediary Discussion

Industry engagement with stakeholders, citizens and consumers, as the preceding sections have illustrated, serve a variety of purpose. Respondents have defined engagement as a way to understand customer needs, a means to advertise their products and create new market opportunities, or as a technique for lobbying and influencing political and regulatory decision making. Only some interviews expressed an understanding of engagement that corresponded to the idea of engagement as defined in European public sector RRI frameworks, i.e., as a way to explore citizen and other stakeholder opinions to align innovation processes with societal needs, values and challenges. Many firms seem far from implementing this ideal of broad stakeholder engagement and mutual responsiveness.

While the examples above came mostly from respondents in low and middle income countries, similar findings were reported in studies on RRI in industry from Europe. Auer and Jarmai (2017) as well as Owen, Ladikos and Forsberg (2017) report, that many industry innovators in SMEs had difficulties to conceptualize the idea of engagement, as used in European RRI discourse. As the sections above show, various respondents provided vague answers, and referred to collaborations with universities or other firms rather to engagement with citizens or the wider public.

Due to the limited amount of data, and the similarity of the findings above with results from studies on the interplay between RRI in Europe, we are not able to draw conclusions about regional variation. Instead, our data indicate that firms in both, high income and middle and lower income countries approach ideas

and practices of stakeholder and citizen engagement, mainly from a financial and market oriented perspective, in which engagement with different publics also served the purpose of corporate image management and maintaining public trust. A concern with wider, longer-term societal impacts was once again absent.

4.2.3. Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion

Gender equality, as defined by the United Nations Entity for Gender Equality, refers to “the equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities of women and men” at all ages, including childhood.⁴ It implies, “that the interests, needs and priorities of both women and men are taken into consideration, recognizing the diversity of different groups of women and men” and the circumstances and socio-cultural contexts they live in.⁵ The term diversity refers to the acknowledgement and affirmation of individual human differences along a variety of dimensions, qualities and characteristics. These include nationality, ethnicity, race, age, gender, sexual orientation, health, physical abilities, religion and socio-economic status among many others. Historically, human diversity has been linked to processes of inclusion and exclusion, with social exclusion manifest in forms of discrimination, unequal access to opportunities and disadvantaged life circumstances. For these reasons, RRI and other policy frameworks stress inclusion, in order to create a culture that embraces diversity and that strives for a culture of equality, justice as well as fair and equal access to opportunities, including those arising from innovation processes.

RRING interviews explored the relevance of diversity and gender equality in the context of respondents’ work and work environment. However, the term diversity was not operationalized or broken down into different dimensions. Most of the selected interviews with private sector innovators focus mainly on the theme of gender equality. Only some interviews discuss aspects related to diversity.

4.2.3.1. The value of diversity

Several interviewees stressed the positive value of diversity and how diversity of peoples’ origins, backgrounds and experiences can enrich innovation processes.

The researchers’ work requires creativity, pro-activity, ability to learn from other experiences, [and to] see and analyze things in an unconventional and precisely innovative way. I believe that multi-disciplinary, multi-sectoral research teams, made up of people from different cultures, experiences and places can represent a great resource for research work. (Interview Italy Nr 2, large company, ICT sector, male)

While the respondent above points to the potential of diversity among researchers and staff to serve as a resource for research and innovation work, the following quotation emphasizes the need to be aware of – and respond to - diversity in society as a whole.

I think [diversity] is highly relevant because, as we've talked a lot about the interaction between research and society, if you're only talking to a small perhaps unrepresentative side of society, you're not going to get the full picture. So, I think that is really an important part, [to have] lots of types of people involved in your organization. I think we'll get a much better understanding of how society generally is thinking, and we can prepare better for how society is going to react to what we're doing. (Interview UK Nr. 1, large company, bioeconomy, male)

According to this respondent, to embrace diversity and understand different perspectives in society has distinct advantages for industry innovators: it helps to understand the needs and views of diverse clients and to “prepare for how society is going to react to what we're doing” (*ibid.*).

⁴ <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/conceptsanddefinitions.htm>

⁵ <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/conceptsanddefinitions.htm>

4.2.3.2. Perceptions of gender equality

Gender equality was in many interviews defined as important goal. Some respondents stated that their firms had achieved a gender balanced employment ratio, but we are not in the position to verify these statements. As the quote below shows, in some cases gender equality was realized because female candidates were in average more qualified than their male applicants.

One of our goals is gender equity for a sustainable development, following what the UN says, for example. In our company almost 50% of administration staff are women, and that is not regulated, but this is the reality.

Interviewer: Did you create formal jobs where 50% of these jobs were taking by women?

They were not created. It simply turned out that the [women] who got the jobs, were the ones with more capability of coping the activities that were assigned to them. (Interview Bolivia Nr 8, large firm, waste management, male)

It is not clear whether in this or other examples gender balance was realized in higher-tier, managerial positions. The next quote shows that, at least in some companies, there are active efforts to reach this goal.

Our goal for 2020 is to have half of women in leadership positions. Leadership for people is from board up, not managerial level, because if we look among the managers, we already have a majority of women. Beyond that it has not happened yet, but I'll tell you that we have 38% women in leadership positions today, that's almost 10 points higher than 4 years ago. We have managed [to] have women in positions of leadership that in most of the companies are occupied by men. So, our Industrial Director is a woman, the director of investor relations is a woman, [and] the director of marketing. They are all the women, you have more. (Interview Brazil Nr 1, SME, bioeconomy, female)

4.2.3.3. Practical difficulties to achieve gender equality and inclusion

In contrast to the examples above, many respondents explained that gender equality remained a difficult to achieve ideal in their firms. While the relevance of gender equality was widely acknowledged, their testimonies clarify that it is often not realized in practice.

We don't really look much at the gender issue, for better or worse. We are looking for the person that fits perfectly. It is true that of the high positions I am the only woman, I tell you that [in] the office, I don't know, we are thirty-something [staff]. Of thirty-something we are seven women. [...] Practically all engineers are men. All researchers are men. Development, except a girl who is a bit junior and so on, all are men. (Interview 5.4.7, Spain, SME, ICT sector, female)

The topic is very relevant. [However], we have not been able to address the gender and also the diversity [issue] in a comprehensive way. (Interview Malawi Nr. 5, SME, energy, female).

Various reasons were cited that prevent gender balance and inclusion in private sector innovation, according to respondents. The first refers to differences in cultural norms and expectations:

I was meeting with the prime minister [in Country Y] recently and – the PM's son. And there's different cultural norms in terms of what happens. What's the woman's role after she gets married? Or after – in society, in the family. What's the expectations? And I really – I've had colleagues working alongside female researchers. They get married, they go back to the home. It could be a different state, a place where they don't speak the language in [Country A], but their expectation is that they are at home with the family, making babies, raising babies, et cetera. And so, it's the cultural norm in terms of that. And so, in terms of – how do you get that cultural shift in that regard? (Interview USA Nr. 6, large company, waste sector, male)

Another interviewee refers to the influence of historically evolved patriarchal norms and institutions, in which men traditionally assume leadership roles.

Botswana is a very patriarchal system. It's run by men, with women having some senior roles; but primarily the senior roles in government in the administration, the university and researchers are mostly men. So, I think that's just a cultural issue. It's not to say that women aren't good researchers. We've got some very good women researchers here. But historically, Botswana has been run by men. So, I think I think men get on okay, with men. I think men get okay with women. But perhaps [they] haven't been given the opportunity. Women haven't been given the opportunities that men have. (Interview Botswana Nr 2, large company, ICT, male).

Suspicion towards educated women was another factor that respondents cited:

Well, to be honest, the only thing and this will be total non-sense, but that is my opinion. Education and knowledge [among women] in our country provoke suspicion. And this... I'm talking about my profession, I do not mean that education and knowledge [...] cause revolt, negative effects. [But it] causes suspicion. [...] So, I often find myself condemned just because I know what I'm doing, and I stand firmly behind it. (Interview Serbia Nr. 4, SME, bioeconomy, female).

The next quotation refers to the negative impact of prejudice, and how it can prevent equality and inclusion, not only with regard to gender, but also ethnicity and other diversity dimensions.

The first thing [to be] eliminated [is] prejudice. [It] should no longer be that we do not have a good relationship with Costa Ricans, or that we do not get along with the Argentinians, or that we like Mexicans well anyway. Starting from deep inside of us, to not have these prejudices, [and] to collaborating with each other. From there we [can] start, then [rely on] international regulation. (Guatemala Interview Nr 3, SME, bioeconomy, female)

4.2.3.4. Efforts to achieve gender equality

Various companies tried to overcome these and other difficulties, and to actively improve gender equality and to enable the progression of women to leadership position through targeted training from the start.

Yes. I agree it's difficult in the social structure from where we come, but we have been making sure that at the starting level itself, for the graduates that we induct, we ensure that there is a healthy percentage of the gender diversity, so that by the time people learn over the years, then they are ready to immediately take up the leadership roles. From five years, seven years in the company, we start ensuring that people start taking lead roles. That's how when you train a lot of gender diversity within the company, then you grow the talent also. It's a part of the initiative from the grassroots level itself. [...] These values are very important for the organization as such and we are continuously driving it. In fact, we have one of the best gender ratios in the country and maybe internationally also, but I haven't seen that benchmark. All reviews, almost all reviews we check what is the gender diversity, and what is the proportion of female leaders that we have and we continue to keep encouraging them to grow. (Interview 5.2.4. India, large company, energy sector, male)

We address gender [inequalities] every day. We need to make sure of that. We need more women in the science space. We can't always be men; I need another Gaopalelwe who is my counterpart, a female counterpart. Most of the time, even with the allocation with the work, there is always an ensuring that the gender operative is established and maintained and sustained so that we move the country forward. (Interview Zambia, Nr. 1, SME, energy sector, male)

One way through which this firm seeks to increase the number of female researchers and employees is to reach out to universities and to engage with female students at career expos:

[W]hen we do career expos, [...] when we do public engagement [...] we always specifically try to engage more female members, female students. Trying to create [an] interest into the nuclear industry so that we bring more females [into our firm]. So, there are many ways [with which] we try to address [inclusion of women]. We also go to schools, go to universities and create that sort of interest, like how can nuclear [energy] ensure that this country's issues are addressed. [...] It's

a multi-faceted approach that we have been taking to address the issues of gender. (same respondent as above)

4.2.3.5. Intermediary Discussion

Many respondents considered diversity and inclusion an important issue, that required active consideration in industry innovation. Most of the selected interviews discussed issues related to gender equality. Other diversity dimensions were not systematically discussed. A central finding from the above-sections is that gender, diversity and inclusion was mainly discussed in relation to researchers and staff. An awareness of diversity issues in the context of society as whole, for example in relation to unequal access to the benefits and products of innovation, was less pronounced. Gender equality was widely considered an important goal and various respondents mentioned that their firms had implemented active measures to achieve a balanced employment ratio. However, it also became apparent that there are substantial challenges to achieve gender equality and inclusion. Various problems were reported. These ranged from gender-specific expectations to the prevalence of patriarchal norms and institutions, as well as prejudices towards highly educated women. Most of these problems were reported from lower and middle income countries in Latin America as well as Africa, but respondents from the USA and Spain also acknowledged that gender equality and other diversity dimensions were not taken serious enough. Respondents from India and Zambia reported that their companies tried to overcome these and other challenges, and to improve gender equality in the context of education and employment, and to actively enable the progression of women to leadership position

4.2.4. Industry innovation and societal needs

The next section explores perceptions on the role of industry and industry innovators to address societal needs. The idea to align the process and outcomes of innovation with the values and needs of society is a central theme in European RRI discourse (Owen, MacNaghten, Stilgoe 2012; Guston 2014). But how do private sector researchers and industry leaders define and think about societal needs, and in which ways do they believe industry should respond to societal challenges, if at all?

4.2.4.1. Perceptions of societal needs

Interviewees mentioned various ways in which their companies seek to address societal needs and challenges, depending on industry sector and the types of products, technologies or services their firms develop and sell.

Economic and social development

For some respondent, addressing societal needs meant primarily to contribute to economic development and growth, which from their perspective, benefits society as a whole. The following interviewee, for example, who works for a large mining company in India, stressed how the firm's activities to produce aluminum and zinc, have contributed to employment and growth:

[Our] primary motive [is] working towards the welfare of society in general. [We] produce, you know, 1.75 million tons of aluminum at one place [and] 2.5 million tons, another place. And then zinc is produced. All this is targeted not just at the economic welfare of the nation, but also the development of the society. [...] So, overall, when we engage with the society, we involve people in employment. And economic welfare is also there; and people understand it. There are some nitty gritty and teething troubles here and there, but they are only teething troubles. Once it goes through, society enjoys it. And I think all economic activities should be directed towards social venture. That's just the best way to go about it. (Interview India, Nr. 6, large company, energy and mining sector, male).

This uncritical belief in the social benefits of industrial growth is not without problems of course, and ignores potential adverse effects of industrial development, possible disruptive effects on local

communities, and environmental damages that result from mining and the production of metal as industrial commodities (Dolan and Rajak 2016). However, we leave this as a situated statement that provides insights into the spectrum of beliefs and ideas through which respondents conceptualize how their firms define and address societal needs. As we will discuss further below in this section, the adoption of a language of societal needs is in some cases closely related to processes of public image management, even though this is not always the case.

Responding to the needs and problems of local communities

For other respondents, addressing societal needs meant especially to recognize and respond to the needs and problems of local communities. For the interviewee below, local needs should be the departure of any innovation that is introduced in a specific context:

For me, especially in the rural context, if you're bringing an innovation, it has to address the needs of the people that are there. Like, for example, [...] where we've brought in innovations like sanitation market. I'll speak for my sector. Sanitation marketing essentially is aiming to ensure that people pay for sanitation services. Either a slab for their toilet or a new toilet or someone who comes to empty their pit, whatever. But it's around sanitation and they have to pay for it. Cool idea. It's got all the principles of demand and supply. (Interview Nr. 5.2.9, Malawi, SME, bioeconomy, male).

Several respondents, in particular in developing countries, mentioned that their firms sought to develop simple, but effective technology solutions, that can address local or regional problems such as pollution or unemployment, while simultaneously generating new forms of income.

Egypt has a big problem in the waste sector, either industrial as well as domestic and local waste. We have a success story with one of our factories. They used to bury their waste in the desert, we made some research and figured out that it could be recycled to be used for animal or bird's food. Waste is a huge asset in Egypt that is not utilized or addressed well. Also, the ways to manage it, is not properly addressed. Such ways will have a big return on the economy and result in a [positive] environmental impact. (Interview Nr. 10, Egypt, large firm, waste sector, male).

A traditional form of what we recycle consists in holding the rubber [waste] and to put it into the crushing machine to get powdered rubber, which become the end input for the tires. In this case we created a circular economy that goes from the first actors who are the saddlers, [rubber workers], who dedicate themselves to make sandals, rubber belts, they generate residues; which we buy to turn them into rubber grain and then into [tires and other rubber products]. (Interview Morocco Nr. 5, SME, waste management, female).

To what extent the development of profitable innovations that are able to address local problems and the needs of local communities is realized in other firms, we do not know. However, these examples indicate, that at least for some firms the aspiration to generate solutions to social challenges serves as an important driver in corporate-based innovation.

Addressing environmental problems

The development of new solutions to environmental problems and the adjustment of private sector innovation and production processes to reduce the negative impact of industrial production on the environment was another theme that respondents mentioned.

[Our] company is fighting for a healthier life, fighting for environmental protection and fighting for sustainability. But really, for sustainable development, not only as a phrase and a story. We are the only example of a circular economy in the region. Last year, the OECD invited us to the conference of the Western Balkans and Turkey as the only company in the area that is really dealing with the circular economy. [...] I think that what we do, can absolutely cause some kind of positive effect. (Interview Serbia Nr. 4, SME, bioeconomy, female).

On the one hand, aligning our action with social challenges is one of the cornerstones of our policy. We believe that all the issues on the building sector will find many solutions that can significantly

contribute to the solution of some of the great social challenges of the coming decades. The increased urbanization, the challenge on CO2 emissions, energy efficiency, mobility, aging are all issues that are seen as one of the keystones in the construction and planning of sustainable growth and sustainable regeneration. (Interview UK Nr 1, SME, bioeconomy, male).

Both of these examples illustrate a firm belief in the possibility of private sector innovation to reduce environmental problems. However, as we will show in the next section, in some cases testimonies to contribute to solutions for grand challenges are mostly rhetorical, services firms themselves rather than society or the environment.

4.2.4.2. Motivations to address societal needs

Corporations face an ongoing struggle to balance competitiveness with economic survival and the need to generate support for new products and innovations among customers and the public at a more general level. Lack of attention to public concerns or needs, can easily result in innovation failure and cause economic losses to firms. For this reason, corporate motivations to engage with societal or environmental needs, do inevitably serve multiple purposes. While aspirations to address societal problems, as some of the examples above have shown, may often be based on upright (e.g. community-oriented) intentions, in a firm's struggle to survive and expand, language and activities that promise answers to societal challenges also can create legitimacy, establish a firm as a responsible player and establish trust among different public and shareholders. This is illustrated through the following two examples. Both reveal also how conceptions of societal needs are influenced by the particularities of (and stakeholders involved in) particular innovation fields.

Industry's need for legitimacy and public support

The first example comes from the domain of agricultural industrial biotechnology (IB), a field of growing importance in the contemporary bioeconomy, much attention is paid to the role and wellbeing of farmers, who are not only the key agents (and targets) to implement agricultural change, but also the first who suffer if IB technologies do not yield the economic, environmental or societal benefits, that this sector promises (Larson et al. 2004; Jain 2010). A concern with the wellbeing and benefits of IB innovation for farmers and farming systems, is in itself an indication of how this sector seeks to address societal needs. However, as the quotation below illustrates, a key concern for the agricultural IB field is to influence public opinion, so that genetically modified crops are seen as providing necessary contributions to food sustainability, for example in the context of climate change. This change in narrative, from conceptualizing societal needs in terms of the sector's potential benefits for farmers, to the benefits for society as a whole, is seen as necessary to create legitimacy and public support for a sector, that is often confronted with criticism.

I think one of the things that we work on, in agriculture, is that probably we focus a little bit too much on the benefits to the farmer and not [...] enough how we benefit to society generally. In fact, I think you can say that [the main story is] about farming. Perhaps in Europe people don't value farming particularly. They are well fed and don't see that we need to encourage [new forms of] farming. So, sometimes it can be quite hard to convince people that you need to innovate in agriculture. [They ask:] Why do we need genetically modified crops, if we have enough food? [But], how do we know that we can continue to produce enough food given the unpredictability of the changing environment, and so on? So, I think that there is an element of what we try to do is to demonstrate that agriculture is sort of the foundation of society really because farmers can produce food efficiently and effectively that we all have more free time to do other more exciting things. (Interview UK Nr. 1, SME, bioeconomy, male).

Alignment with sustainability goals as a form of corporate branding

The second example comes from the nuclear science and energy sector. The quotation below illustrates how innovators in this field, strategically frame potential benefits in the language of the UN's sustainable development goals (SDG):

Nuclear science and technology offer a lot of [...] opportunities. Look at the sustainable developmental goals, seventeen of them, nuclear technologies can play a part in all those seventeen sustainable development goals. I mean, look at issues of drought, nowadays we need to be more involved on drought resistant crops that can sustain and ensure food security. We have issues of diseases that we treat in the nuclear science and technology, for example, how to better treat cancer. Someone was sharing with us very interesting research they are doing in the UK which uses Radium. (interview South Africa Nr. 1, large company, energy, male).

While we cannot prove these claims, nor doubt that the respondent believes in the reported benefits, the quotation shows, that the UN's SDGs and other grand challenges can be used in strategic ways to represent the possible benefits of emerging technologies, in order to mobilize public support and pre-empt public criticism. However, as several studies have shown, in practice these promises are often exaggerated and misleading (Master and Resnick 2013). Not only exist in many technology fields uncertainties whether promised benefits can be achieved, or whether a specific technology field (such as nuclear science) offers the best possible solutions to a particular problem, but the framing of an emerging innovation's potential to address global challenges such as drought and climate change, invites also to downplay or ignore potential risks and adverse effects, including the risk of unintentional societal and environmental consequences (Rosemann and Molyneux-Hodgson 2020).

4.2.4.3. Intermediary Discussion

A central finding of our analysis is that many respondents considered the alignment of innovation processes with societal challenges and problems as an important goal, including in most non-European countries where the US-European RRI discourse does not play a role in national innovation policies. As mentioned in Section 4.1 above, various respondents from lower and middle income countries thought that industry innovation should not only maximize profits but play an active role in the development of local communities and the realization of social progress. Similar ideas resurfaced in this section (4.2.4). Most of the quoted text passages above come from respondents from Latin American and African countries, as well as India. Virtually of all these people stressed that it was important that innovation work in their firms would correspond to local needs and contribute to problems that people in their societies faced. We are unable to confirm, however, to what extent this ideal was realized or is representative of the perceptions of corporations in these regions at a more general level. Unsurprisingly, however, as in Section 4.1. above, various respondents stressed that the realization of social progress was feasible only, if part of a viable business model that would allow companies to survive and flourish.

5. Results part 2: Drivers of RRI in industry

A common distinction in the literature on RRI in industry is between external and internal drivers that influence the adoption and use of RRI ideas in private sector innovation. External drivers encompass factors such as policy principles, regulatory and legal frameworks, professional standards, or the requirements of public funding bodies (Martinuzzi and Jarmai 2019). But external drivers can also include pressures from civil society, expectation of customers or the need to comply with third party stakeholders such as academic collaborators, supply or distribution companies or the motivation to avoid negative media coverage (Auer and Jarmai 2018).

Internal drivers, on the other hand, refer to factors that promote RRI adoption within firms or research organization. These can include institutional policies that promote principles such as gender equality, diversity and inclusion, or unspoken norms such as a shared commitment to eco-friendly innovation that is representative of a specific ethos in an organizational culture (Stahl 2018). A related internal driver are the motivations, values and moral standards of corporate decision makers and staff, and the ways in which these inform corporate decision-making and the development of new products and services (Schoenherr, Martinuzzi and Jarmai 2020). In practice, external and internal drivers can be closely inter-twined. External drivers such as government regulations or public expectations inevitably influence institutional policies (cf.

Bessant and Iakovleva 2019; Divella and Sterlacchini 2019). And policy aspirations such as the UN SDGs, on the other hand, can influence people's motivations, an organizations cultural values, and direct innovation processes into specific directions.

In the following we will explore external and internal drivers to the adoption of RRI ideas, as expressed in the RRING interviews with industry innovators. Most of the literature above has explored perceptions of corporate innovators in a European and US-American context. The RRING interviews, in turn, introduce relevant perspectives from corporate leaders and staff from lower and middle income countries.

5.1. External Drivers

Respondents mentioned a wide variety of external drivers that directly or indirectly stimulate the adoption of, or engagement with RRI or RRI-like ideas. In the European Union, at least for corporate researchers that received funding from public research councils, the RRI Keys, Science with and for Society, and in the UK the AREA frameworks, played of course a central role. However, because in this report we are mostly interested in the perceptions and practices of industry innovators that do not receive public funding, and that live and work in other world parts, we will not examine the role of formalized RRI frameworks in the EU (a comprehensive overview of this has been published by Schoenherr, Martinuzzi and Jarmai 2020).

A first group of external drivers that respondents mentioned were policy drivers that ranged from policies and regulation that promoted diversity and gender equality, environmental policies and standards, employment rights, to more specific regulations, such as safety protocols for GMOs or nuclear safety analysis. In the next paragraphs we provide some examples of respondents' views on the role of policies that promote gender equality as well as environmental protection.

5.1.1. Policies that promote gender equality

Several research participants stated that the existence of gender policy at a national level has a discernible effect in the firms for which they work. A respondent from Morocco, for example, mentioned that:

Morocco has signed a lot of decrees on the equality of sexes and women; especially in the different sectors that women have not had the right to exercise. I would say for example we have women working in the mechanical [engineering], chairwomen. So, in Morocco we do not have this problem that women are working only in the trade [sector]. And in our association, we have a president woman and I recruited a female engineer and a woman marketer. That means that the sexes equality does not pose any problems. (Interview Morocco Nr. 2, large firm, energy, male).

Another respondent from Morocco also stated that the government's gender policy has an effect in companies and that employers have changed recruitment practices, as a result of it. However, it is not clear whether the policy also affects the ratio between man and women in the sciences, or in high level managerial positions. Moreover, while the policy affects decisions in HR departments, it does not promote reflection on the gendered dimensions of new innovations in the context of their commercialization and daily use.

Another example comes from Malawi, where both government and universities promote gender equality, and encourage participation of women in domains and positions that were previously mainly occupied men. As a result of a lower number of female students, some universities have introduced "deliberate policies to accept [more female] students. [Universities] will take 30% female students [as a minimum, accepting lower entry requirements], and then the rest come in as in normal acceptance" (Interview Malawi Nr. 2, large firm, ICT sector, male).

Both of these examples confirm that gender policies around the world are gradually changing attitudes and result in increased access to education and more equal participation, at least in some innovation domains. However, these policies do not focus on the gendered aspects of innovation processes themselves, for example whether new technologies or products will be available equally across the genders, and also how new innovation can influence the relationships between men and women, at the level of the family, local

communities, the workplace or other areas of social life. This is a fundamental difference with how gender equality is conceptualized in European RRI policies.

5.1.2. Environmental policies and standards

The existence of national and international environmental policies and regulatory instruments and standards was another type of policy driver that research participants mentioned, which facilitated RRI-like practices to some extent. A respondent who works for a large company in the Indian energy sector, for example, mentioned that:

There are very stringent environmental norms [...] for the thermal plants [that we run], and those match any developed country and in fact we have a come at par with them. In fact, for renewable energy, we [in India] are giving far more incentives than the developed countries. We are third in rank above the U S which is a 50th in rank. So, all those things are there. I think that is a very strong law and regulatory. Um, what should I say, a standard of performance which binds us, and we are following that even at the cost of industry's growth. (Interview India Nr 6, large company, energy sector, male).

This quotation refers to both, the restrictive role of law and regulation that affects performance standards in firms, and the enabling role of policy incentives and funding that encourage the development of renewable energies. An issue that is not mentioned here, but which is relevant in large middle-income countries such as China, India, Brazil and Russia, is the capacity of national governments to effectively implement legal and regulatory frameworks across the large number of institutions, factories and commercialization networks that exist in these countries.

Interestingly, the following quotation from a private sector manager in the energy sector in Brazil, shows that implementation of external rules depends in part on grassroots participation, partly through the involvement of skilled staff from within companies.

We are [adhering to the rules of] external, environmental regulatory institutes, such as [those issued by] the Brazilian Institute of Environment and Renewable Natural Resources. So, these are rules dictated by the great formal and normative external apparatus. Now, there is an important question that is crucial to us, which is the fact that a lot of our [researchers] here, because of their technical profiles and skills, end up participating in governmental instances. Some have already been secretaries for the environment, secretary of energy, and so on. So, this ends up in a non-formal, unstructured way, being a two-way street in this sense as well. Participation in these instances, governmental or nongovernmental, ends up bringing in and taking these concerns from the inside out, which are gaining form here (Interview Brazil 2, large firm, energy sector, male).

While more information would be required to fully evaluate this situation, it seems obvious that there is an important conflict of interest here, in which government rules and their implementation are co-shaped by experts and staff employed by industry. On the other hand, the active participation of people who are or at least were employed by the private sector, is likely to provide new opportunities for bottom-up regulatory initiatives that would otherwise be ignored by government, or that are implemented outside of formal government regulatory frameworks. An unresolved question is of course, who benefits from the close intertwinement of firms and government in the regulation of industry innovation in Brazil's energy sector. Are the primary beneficiaries corporations, because they are able to shape a regulatory environment that corresponds to their needs and that translates into more profits, or citizens and local communities, because the possibility to influence government regulation facilitates more effective forms of corporate self-governance and possibly (as the quotation above seems to indicate) new pathways to the development and use of renewable energy sources?

5.1.3. Lack of policies to promote RRI-like ideas in some countries

While a larger number of respondents elaborated on the ways in which state policy and regulation in the above and other areas influenced innovation processes in the context of their work, others pointed to shortcomings and lack of regulation. The following quotation, for example, suggests that upstream innovation decisions and practices often fall below the radar of existing regulation. Regulatory rules,

according to this respondent from India, apply mostly when a project reaches the stage of implementation and commercialization. Upstream R&D and innovation activities within firms, on the other hand, are mostly self-governed.

For [upstream] innovation, I would say, uh, there aren't a lot of regulatory rules that are required. Uh, I mean innovation [takes] mostly [place] within the organization. So, from the government's side or a regulatory approval side, [rules are] there only when the project reaches a certain stage, [when] the project enters into a phase of implementation. [But even] then, the approvals [that] are required are few in number. [...] So, there is very limited regulatory approval, I would say compliance approval that is required. (Interview India Nr 6, large company, energy sector, male).

This quotation indicates that existing regulation in several sectors and countries around the world provides only partial coverage of the concerns and issues that RRI-related ideas promote. A more reflective and inclusive engagement with the longer-term consequences and societal impact of emerging innovations at an upstream level is, at least according to the above respondent, often absent. Other interviews indicate however that the extent of regulatory intervention varies significantly between sectors and countries.

5.1.4. Sustainable Development Goals

Another external driver to the adoption of RRI-like practices that industry innovators mentioned were the UN SDGs. The SDGs, as pointed out in Section 4.2.4 above, play an important role in the aligning of innovation processes with societal and environmental needs. As the following quotation shows, ideas promoted by the UN SDGs clearly influence innovation decisions, at least in some firms:

Zero harm and zero discharge [is] one of the pillars of our organization. [We] understand that safety as well as low emissions and sustainable development is the key to progress in the near future. (Interview India Nr 6, large company, energy sector, male).

While we do not have strong evidence in the interviews with industry innovators that SDGs have actively influenced innovation agendas within firms, several interviewees have mentioned that the broader aims and values that the SDGs reflect, are adopted in firms as aspirations that are sought to be realized over time:

[Ideas such as] “do not pollute”, “do not contaminate”, to have processes that are sustainable over time; these are targeted at [our firm] and can broaden the possibilities for those who are participating [in innovation decisions]. (Interview Brazil 1, large firm, bioeconomy, female).

We set up a set of practices in order to respect the principles of sustainable development, that is to say be economically viable, have a positive impact on society but also better respect the environment. (Interview Morocco Nr. 1, large firm, energy, male)

5.2. Internal Drivers

Social science literature on the internal drivers for the adoption of RRI in industry, has distinguished between instrumental and moral motives (Garst et al. 2017; Martinuzzi et al 2018). Instrumental motives encompass aspirations such as the generation of new profits, or to use RRI to prevent public controversy and/or to legitimize controversial technologies or products. Moral motives, on the other hand, reflect ethical and normative convictions or consideration that influence how responsibility is defined, and in which ways innovation processes can contribute to a common good or are done in ways that prevent harm or other problematic consequences. However, as Garst and colleagues have suggested, moral motives are frequently closely intertwined with instrumental motives. Given the pressure of firms to navigate a complex and competitive environment, moral agency or motivations to adhere to specific norms can often not be separated from endeavors to manage stakeholder relations, create a favorable public image, or to create a constructive business environment. Indeed, these authors conclude, that instrumental motives are a central requirement for the realization of responsible innovation in the private sector and play a key role in the development of responsible products (Garst et al. 2017).

Several of the previous sections have already referred to the role of strategic and instrumental motives to RRI adoption. While the main emphasis in this section lies on the role of moral motives and convictions, we want to summarise these briefly. A first point, made in Section 4.1.5, was that the realization of societal benefits must have the potential to be transformed into profits. Only then it is usually seen as a path worthwhile to pursue. Second, sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2 have shown that many firms use RRO components such as anticipation or engagement with different stakeholders strategically, for example in order to improve a company's reputation, better understand customer needs and identify new marketing practices, or to develop ways to influence political and regulatory decision making and to change public opinion. Third, section 4.2.4 has illustrated that motivations to address societal and environmental needs and challenges were also often driven, at least in part, by firms' desire to create legitimacy and public or political support for new innovations and products, especially if these were based on the use of controversial technologies such as genetic engineering or nuclear technology applications. In the next sections we will examine statements and views that reflect "moral motives" to the adoption of RRI-like ideas among respondents, and also explore whether or to what extent these relate to more instrumental internal drivers.

5.2.1. Internalized value convictions and moral norms

A central theme that respondents referred to was internalized norms and ideas of responsibility, that influenced how they thought about their role and the implications of their work:

We must increasingly be an example in our lines of action, in our behavior of dialogue with the public [and] with institutions. Therefore, considering the impact that our actions, our research will have on the public, in general, and on the development of the environments in which we operate, means considering the impacts on the many areas of people's lives. (Interview Italy Nr. 3, SME, ICT, female).

We are all responsible of our work and the achievement of the goals we are also responsible of the well being of people working with us, we are responsible of how our work impact the society and also the future I think we are responsible of everything that is related directly or indirectly to our work. (Interview Morocco Nr. 7, SME, ICT, male).

You have to respect other people's rights, make sure that in whatever you are doing there has to be consent, issues of privacy. When you are respecting other peoples' rights, everything goes well. You don't have to impose anything on them. (Interview Malawi Nr. 3, large firm, energy, male)

According to several interviewees, these internalized norms and moral convictions facilitate a reflective awareness of their research and work, including of its implications, and form a vital precondition for the adoption of RRI-like activities at the level of actual practice.

Responsibility needs to... it comes with planning, it's not something that you can reverse engineer and build it into a product or build it into a practice. It has to be thought of first. [...] Like: "Why are we doing this and what are the implications of doing it?" (Interview UK 2, Large firm, ICT, female).

In general, the values of a company are always done by the people that are directing the company. [...]

In my opinion, the main rule is the culture. If you really want to make a change, [it] is a question of empowering the people; to design capacity building activities, to really raise awareness and inform the people. So, the cultural change should not be imposed by laws, but rather the role of laws is to support transversal activities that can really drive the change by empowering the people. We believe that it can have an impact, otherwise, it is just an additional directive or an additional law that people are trying to find the way to overcome somehow. (Interview Italy Nr. 2, large firm, ICT, female).

Both of these statements point to the fact that change (in this case the adoption of RRI-like practices in firms), starts "within" – within individuals, within the people who direct a company, and within the

organizational culture, in which new innovations are developed and commercialised. The second respondent also refers to the role of law or regulations in instilling or enforcing RRI-related ideas or practices, and concludes that if internal awareness or motivation to achieve change is absent within individuals and the culture of a firm or research institute, external rules are likely to be met with resistance, insufficiently implemented, and if possible circumvented.

5.3 Intermediary Discussion

The previous sections introduced a variety of both external and internal drivers to the adoption of RRI or RRI-like ideas in industry contexts. External drivers that respondents mentioned included environmental policies and standards, employment rights as well as policies and regulation that promoted diversity, inclusion and gender equality. In the European Union, at least in firms that received seed funding from European funding bodies, RRI frameworks such as AREA and RRI Keys played also a role, at least in the context of specific projects. Other external drivers that seem to promote the adoption of RRI-like practices are the UN SDGs, which were mentioned by respondents from India, Brazil and Morocco. Respondents from Europe and other high-income countries, at least in the sample of interviews we used, did not refer to the role of UN SDGs in promoting RRI-like practices, even though SDGs were mentioned in other contexts. A few respondents complained about the lack of policies that could promote RRI-like ideas in their country. A respondent from India, for example, stated that upstream innovation decisions are not usually considered by existing regulation, which focus mainly on commercial translation and use.

Due to the limited number of interviews that were available for this report, we are not able to provide a comparative overview of which kinds of regulations, policies, standards, or other external drivers promote the adoption of RRI-like ideas in specific countries or global regions, let alone to discuss how these instruments are implemented and what effect they have. This would require separate and more in-depth research. Nevertheless, our data reveal that external drivers, as for instance gender and diversity policies, or employment laws, have a clear impact at the level of actual practices, even though challenges exist in some countries to implement these policies evenly. A more general issue is that, even though gender and diversity policies can change attitudes and increase access to more equal participation in the context of education, scientific research and employment, these policies do not usually focus on the gendered aspects of innovation processes themselves. As the testimonies from Malawi and Morocco in Section 5.1.1 show, gender policies in these countries have changed recruitment practices, but they do not provide instruments to assure that new technologies, products or services will be available equally to men and women. They also do not invite reflection on whether innovation processes can change the relationship between the genders, at the level of households, at work, or in the organization of local communities.

Internal drivers included internalized moral norms, beliefs and value convictions, which instill reflective thinking on innovation processes, at least in some respondents. Awareness of societal and environmental problems and the experience of poverty, deprivation and lack of opportunities, formed another source of motivation for change and reflection of more responsible, inclusive and sustainable forms of innovation, especially among respondents responsible and sustainable innovation.

6. Results Part 3: Challenges to the adoption of RRI in industry

6.1. Frictions between public sector and industry RRI

Various studies that have examined the feasibility and use of RRI ideas in industry in the context of the European Union, have concluded that there is misalignment of existing RRI concepts with the characteristics of industry innovation, and the needs and priorities of industry at a more general level

(Dreyer et al. 2017; Lubberink et al. 2017; Stahl et al. 2019). In the following paragraphs we will explore these friction points and examine the challenges that arise to the adoption and implementation of RRI-like ideas, as articulated by industry innovators interviewed for the RRING project.

6.1.1. No need to comply with the rules of public funding bodies

A first, more general point is that firms do not need to comply with the expectations or rules of public funding bodies. While the implementation of RRI-like ideas varies significantly between countries, this frees firms to conform with the ethical and responsibility requirements that are typically attached to public funding, except they are recipient of such funding. As the following quotation shows, this frees

[My] previous experience [at a university] was, we followed the guidance from the funders in that we always had to provide impact statements, just to apply for the funding. And in doing that, we knew that our projects had to align with the expected outcomes and the expected impacts from the funder. And so, we would align ourselves to that. But now, working for a private company, we are not chasing [public] funding, [...] so we don't have a strong need to align with these, with the impact that the funder is expecting. That's normally something that is addressed by the more academic partners or somebody else that is leading the consortium. (Interview UK Nr. 2, large firm, ICT, female)

Yet, while independence from public funding prevents the need to comply with the rules of public funding bodies, there are other pressures that firms are subjected to, be it from the side of customers, shareholders, as well as regulators and the wider public.

6.1.2. Pressure to deliver can prevent engagement with RRI-like ideas

Indeed, the pressure of companies, especially SMEs and start-ups, to deliver new, profitable innovations and products form another challenge to the adoption of RRI-like ideas. While firms must find a balance between responding to public and customers concerns, and the expectations arising from the dependency on banks and private financiers, the need for ongoing cash-flows to invest in R&D and to pay salaries and operation expenses, can make the engagement with RRI or RRI-like ideas to a low priority issue, especially if not related to immediate financial profits or other benefits.

[As] a start-up, a for-profit company, [...] of course, you need funding to do the work. So how can someone fund you. Pretty much asking high-net worth individuals. You're gonna be asking accelerators, grant-giving institutions that are interested in certain avenues, trying to go after people providing equity-free grant funding at first in the angel stage, early investing. Then later on, maybe you're going for more like a VC kind of venture capital round and more Series-A funder or a seed funder, larger organization. (Interview USA Nr. 6., large firm, waste sector, male)

As the following quotation shows, after funding has been received, investors can exert potential influence on firm decisions; including on the timing and under which conditions a new product is put on the market:

You can imagine a case where [...] investors have a majority in the company and they're willing to say, "Well, okay, this is not 100% healthy yet, but we got to put it to market anyway." That's a very hypothetical thing which is definitely not something [our company] is close to. But you can imagine such a case. Such cases, of course, have happened in the feed and food industry. (Interview 5.2.2., UK, SME, bioeconomy, male).

The same respondent pointed out, that there is clear danger that financial pressure in companies, and sometimes perhaps outright greed, can result in firms cutting corners on the implementation of safety measures and other RRI aspects:

[There is] the possibility to cut corners in the safety aspect. This would be unethical, but there is a possibility in any one of the five companies [I talked about], also the four others could do that, to get a competitive advantage. But it would kill our type of industry, and it would definitely also kill

a person or multiple persons working for the company. You should just not cut those corners, but I imagine that in other industries in the past, and even maybe now that has happened that they cut corners. This is an ethical thing, and as I said sometimes, yes, sorry, I don't. (Interview 5.2.2., UK, SME, bioeconomy, male)

These examples point to a key difference between public sector funded and privately funded innovation processes in firms. While reliance on public funding comes with clear expectations to adhere to the ethical and responsibility policies attached to public sector money, dependency on money from private investors arrives first of all with the expectation to deliver innovation outcomes and generate economic revenues fast. These expectations can influence the extent, purposes, and contexts in which RRI or RRI-like ideas are adopted, and the ways they are operationalized and implemented.

6.1.3. Tensions between open science and the need for secrecy in industry innovation

Blok and Lemmens (2015) and several other authors (e.g. Martinuzzi et al. 2018) have stated that there is a central tension between RRI demands for transparency and open science (which includes open access and open data) and the need for secrecy and closed innovation in industry contexts. This tension was also emphasized by respondents in this study. Both statements indicate that data generated in industry research can be published, as long as they do not prevent the generation of patents and intellectual property or undermine the competitiveness of firms in other ways.

[If we] develop new [...] research we make available data that were generated internally. At times if it is something that can generate intellectual property, [the data] will be more protected [and not shared]. (Interview Brazil Nr 1, large company, bioeconomy, female).

If you go in a proprietary direction, the result of the research can be published according to the constraints of IPR. I do not think that there is an obligation for the public dissemination of the research results, always and in any case. I believe that the Open Access system for research data also takes into account the possibility to not distribute its results, as research must also be a tool to create value for those who invest into research on innovative products that cannot be "Given away" (used by others for business) to the market. In this case, it is important to avoid that no company invests in research. (Interview Italy Nr. 3, large firm, ICT sector, male).

While both of these examples refer to the voluntary character of the open sharing of data and research findings in firms and to the need to withhold some data and research outcomes for the purpose of IPR protection, the second respondents reported to increasing in corporate policies towards open access, with a greater emphasis of sharing and free access, at least in the EU. According to this research participants, "until a few years ago part of the added value of a study or analysis was given by its confidentiality [the ability to deny access to specific information]", but in recent years this aspect has been increasingly "exceeded by the advantage linked to sharing, which allows to grow the visibility, contacts and authority of the organization."

6.1.4. Concerns on open science beyond IPR

Other respondents had a more critical view and raised concerns about the open sharing of data that went beyond concerns on the protection of intellectual property. The following interview excerpt states, for example, that some firms are concerned that open data could be used selectively, which make a company look bad:

Often, we think, well, if we make all of our data available [it is good], but people can analyze those data in a way that would make us look bad. Even though we would say the data [as a whole] don't show that, there are always ways to analyzing data to come up with a conclusion that you want. There is a suspicion, that by making data open we open ourselves up to problems. People who would like to act maliciously against us, by making all our documents available, perhaps we give them an opportunity to do that. So, there's an interesting trade off to be made here. You can see advantages in making your data available, but you can also see disadvantages. (Interview UK Nr. 1, large firm, bioeconomy, male)

Others also expressed concerns that openly shared data could be misused. One interviewee mentioned, for example, that certain types of data can be for dual use purposes or misused in other ways, and should be kept confidential as a result:

In my opinion, publication of research result is very good because we give information to everyone, but there is some information which we have not to be published, because some persons can use it for bad things. So, we have to control what we have, [and what we want] to publish and [where] we [need to be] confidential. (Interview Morocco Nr. 8, large firm, energy, male)

6.2. Political contexts and RRI implementation

As Scherer and Voegtlin (2020) and other authors have pointed out (Long and Blok 2015; Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg 2018), the broader political and socio-economic contexts in which private sector innovation takes place influence the ways in which RRI or RRI-like ideas are understood and implemented in important ways. Owen, Ladikas and Forsberg (2018) have stated in this regard, that national political and cultural contexts form the macro-frameworks that shape how RRI concepts are adopted and used. They argue that, in rapidly developing countries, the realization of fast social and economic development weighs often stronger, than a commitment to sustainability or the prevention of problematic long-term effects of innovation processes.

Our data indicate that political and cultural differences between and within countries, can pose substantial challenges to the acceptance, application and implementation of RRI-like ideas. In the following sections we will discuss four of these challenges: (i) ineffective regulation, (ii) corruption, (iii) insufficient government funding for RRI-related practices, and (iv) over-reliance on NGO funding

6.2.1. When government regulations don't work

A first challenges concerns problems with government regulations. As an industry manager from Guatemala put it: "Many times, [existing] norms and regulation [...] don't have the capacity to delimit the actions [of companies]." (Interview X, Guatemala). This respondent pointed out, that even though certain regulatory rules are in place, specific problems persist, and this undermines trust in both, governance and regulation. The head of a SME in Malawi points to another problem: the fact that some innovation field, in this case ICT, remain almost completely unregulated.

Okay, unfortunately, I think governance, IT governance, let me say a broader view like ICT policy. In Malawi, we're yet to implement most of the proposed policies [...]. ICT is not prioritized here in Malawi as a country. We are yet to do a lot of things. [Only if] all those [regulations] are put in place and well implemented, and we prioritize ICT sector, things may improve in Malawi. (Interview 5.2.6 Malawi, SME, ICT, male)

Corporations are left to self-govern as a result. However, self-governance in the context of a reliable system of exterior standards and rules is difficult and confronts firms with problems of trust and credibility that can have harmful consequences (Sleeboom-Faulkner 2017).

6.2.2. Corruption

Corruption poses another, significant challenge to the adoption of RRI-like ideas, at least in some countries. If regulators and other officials are corrupt, companies can effectively sideline regulatory and legal requirements, and get away with it. This makes the consistent implementation of ethical and regulatory standards, which is a key RRI component, often difficult or impossible. The following quotation provides an example of the head of a company that aimed to implement a circular economy in the tire industry.

I wanted to [build this business] with the endorsement of the Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources. I approached them to see if they could [appraise us], to see how this was done. The answer I found was "look I have a my empresita (my little business) that can support you...". I was being charged an additional fee that was not even a fee from the Ministry, it turned out to be a

personal interest of the official. I was afraid, because they want one to come into their game. So, I no longer wanted to approach the Ministry. [...] It is no secret that the system is corrupted, we must look for a way other than attack. I feel that there are already more bad ones than good ones - perhaps not in the practical world, but in the system of authorities. In the system where formalities need to be done, the good ones become infected and end up being more the bad guys. Then the bad guys are punished, misguided, criticized and can no longer be good. (Interview Guatemala Nr. 3, SME, bioeconomy, female)

If corruption in the government is widespread, as this example indicates, the possibilities for firms to operate outside this system become increasingly difficult.

6.2.3. Governments provide insufficient resources

Another challenge to the adoption of RRI-like practices in some countries, is that governments do not provide sufficient resources to facilitate responsible innovation practices. The following quotation indicates that money for the realization of RRI-like practices, comes in some countries not from government, but from NGOs.

Most of the money that the sector receives comes from donors. Right now, because of the issue of lack of trust in government systems, most of that money is coming through NGOs. It would be the case for the foreseeable future. (Interview 5.2.9 Malawi, SME, bioeconomy, male).

6.2.4. Over-reliance on NGO funding

Financial resources and committed leadership are crucial components for the implementation of RRI. However, the necessity to rely on resources from NGOs, creates its own problems. It creates a dependency on NGOs, and the requirement to follow the agendas and priorities that individual NGOs pursue. But it can also create other problems. As the example below shows, the reliance of NGOs to attract money from donors, can result in false data and misrepresentation of societal needs. The following quotation illustrates this point, with the example of an NGO that assembles money for the creation of water points in Malawi.

I think one of the things I'm learning now, is to recognize dimensions of the political economy of the sector and the incentives that are there. Because I realize that players in the sector behave the way they behave because of the incentives that are there. [Now he starts to explain what he means by referring to NGOs that use false claims to attract donor funding:]. I personally think any NGO should measure their success by how resilient they leave a community, whether they've changed the community from the time they were there and then after. But the incentives here [for some NGOs in Malawi], how can I express this? If people are kept poor, angels have work. [Now he starts to explain this point through a concrete example:]

Just to give you evidence of what I mean. I did a water point mapping in Rumphi District several years ago. I asked the DIS board officer, "How many water points do you think you have?" He said, "1,000." I said, "Okay, fine." As part of budgeting, we bumped it up to 1,250, just for budgeting purposes. When we finished, we found 3,300. He had three times more than what he thought he had. When I took this evidence to some organizations, who were working in the area, to show them that this is an issue, [I said] I think we need to find a way of getting this information to government.

One of the organizations said, "We already knew that." I said, "How come you didn't do anything about it?" They said, "Well, apparently, this information was shared with the government and the government simply said, "Thank you," and put it in a trunk" Reason being if you communicate to donors and NGOs that actually this district does not need any more water points, you just need to invest in maintaining the systems, money dries up.

In this sector, any innovation that comes along, it will have to function in a political economy and it's a political economy that has incentives that try to keep things the way they are. When you bring an innovation that is trying to shift things and it's based on evidence, you have all the evidence, you have all the backing for it, you will still get resistance. (Interview 5.2.9, Malawi, SME, bioeconomy, male).

This quotation is a telling reminder how vested interests, and an established system of mobilizing financial resources from donors, can result in institutionalized fraud, which in this case prevents that the money that this NGO (or possibly several NGOs) generate(s), is used for more urgent issues and in regions where real problem exist.

6.3 Intermediary Discussion

The challenges to the adoption of RRI and RRI-like ideas and policies mentioned above, refer to the role of broader contextual factors such as differences in political systems and cultures, availability of resources or political determination to consistently implement ethical and regulatory frameworks, as well as differences in social and business cultures, in which innovation processes are problematized in different ways, and evaluated through diverging priorities and values. Lack of effective regulation, problems with implementation as well as corruption were especially reported from lower and middle income countries. These factors were seen as important problems that have the potential to sideline or destroy attempts to make science and innovation processes more responsible, fair or inclusive.

A factor that seems to prevent the adoption of RRI-like ideas at a more general level in firms, across all geographies is economic and financial pressure to deliver new innovations and products, which forms a serious obstacle to RRI implementation. In the interviews this point was mainly mentioned by industry staff from the USA and the UK, but in countries like China, India and other middle income countries that try to compete and catch up with economic and technological developments in high income countries, pressure to succeed is possibly even fiercer and demands for RRI and more comprehensive forms of innovation governance, are seen as hindrance rather than an opportunity (Salter et al. 2016; Sleeboom-Faulkner 2016; Lee 2018).

Lack of resources to promote and implement RRI-like ideas was another widely mentioned obstacle in lower and middle income countries. Some respondents complained that the absence of funding by the state, creates an over-reliance on NGOs, which creates its own problems, such as dependency, the need to adjust to the agendas and priorities of NGOs and their donors, and the risk of sudden funding cuts.

7. Concluding Comments

This report has analyzed the ways in which industry leaders, staff and researchers in different regions of the world understand, evaluate and use RRI or RRI-like practices. The conclusions follow the structure of the empirical analysis, which was divided in three parts: understandings, drivers and challenges to the adoption and use of RRI in industry settings.

Understandings of RRI in industry

Formal knowledge of RRI principles, as defined in European policy frameworks, was – as expected - limited among industry innovators around the world. The only countries in which the RRI concept was an active policy concept by funders and firms were the United States and Japan. However, industry innovators from the other geographic regions expressed a wide range of understandings of what responsible innovation means in the context of their work. Understandings of RRI-like practices that emerged in interviews from Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Middle East ranged from ideas of doing “honest” business and the circumventing of illegal practices, to preventing the misuse of corporate power, achieving progress for local communities, and the prevention of environmental damage.

Most of these ideas and described practices are highly compatible with European RRI ideas. However, a difference is that in lower- and middle-income countries, many of the interviewed industry innovators emphasized the need for local development and capacity building, in which profit making was combined with new forms of social development, that create employment and new opportunities. To no surprise, many respondents emphasized that the introduction of RRI-like practices must be balanced with economic success. For some of the interviewees, the generation of value for the firm itself was clearly more important than the creation of value for society. But also those who expressed a strong interest in combining business with social development, stressed that if innovations that have the potential to contribute to common good are not economically viable, they cannot be pursued. As part of our attempt to discern different understandings of RRI we looked at perceptions of the role and value of four central RRI dimensions: understandings of anticipation; engagement; gender, diversity and inclusion; as well as the relationship between industry innovation and societal needs.

Anticipation

Perceptions of the role, value and forms anticipation as a means to work towards responsible industry innovation varied widely and differed in important respects from the ways in which “anticipation” is defined by European public sector funding bodies. Some respondents defined the term simply as a form of business planning and the identification of future opportunities, or as a way to manage economic and technical risks in firms. Others conceived of anticipation as a mechanism to prevent reputation damage, for instance by making sure that partner organizations would not make use of child labor or slave labor practices. Several respondents understood the term as a way to identify negative environmental or societal effects, similar to the European RRI discourse.

Engagement

Many industry innovators in lower- and middle-income countries had difficulties to understand the idea of public engagement, as promoted in European RRI discourse. Answers were often vague and, as with anticipation, understandings of engagement were mostly linked to business needs. Perceptions of the role and possibilities of public and stakeholder engagement ranged from market research (understanding customer needs and identifying new market opportunities), to outreach and communication (changing public opinion and misconceptions), forms of corporate image management, and engagement as a strategy to influence political and regulatory decision making. What these conceptions share, was an interest to understand and read the social environment and value commitments of local communities, and to use this information for business purposes. Some respondents, however, expressed understandings of engagement that went beyond business interests, and that were more in sync with European RRI discourse.

Gender, diversity and inclusion

Most of the selected interviews addressed issues related to gender equality. While other diversity dimensions were not systematically discussed, many respondents in Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Middle East stressed the positive value of diversity and the importance of inclusion, to create equality of opportunities, widespread access to innovation and education, and also to enrich innovation processes by working with people with diverse backgrounds and experiences. Gender equality was widely considered as important goal and many firms reported that they were actively committed to achieve gender equality, also in the context of scientific and higher-tier management positions.

However, the data indicated various challenges to achieve gender equality and inclusion. Problems that were cited included differences in gender-specific norms and expectations, with the prevalence of patriarchal norms and institutions at least in some firms, as well as suspicion towards educated women. Several respondents stated that their companies tried to overcome these difficulties, and to actively improve gender equality and to enable the progression of women to leadership positions.

Industry innovation and societal needs

Many of the interviewed industry innovators considered alignment of innovation processes with societal challenges and problems an important goal, including in most non-European countries where the RRI discourse does not play a role in national innovation policies. Several representatives from industry in low- and middle income considered it crucial that innovation work in their firms would correspond to local needs and problems that people faced. However, as pointed out above, there was widespread consensus that the development of solutions to societal and environmental problems was feasible only, if it was part of a viable business model that would allow companies to make profits, survive and expand. Motivations to address societal needs varied widely. Some admitted that firms' efforts to "do good" and engage with societal problems was mainly a form of image management, through which companies hoped to gain legitimacy and attract public support.

Drivers of the adoption of RRI-like practices in industry

Respondents mentioned a broad range of external drivers that encouraged the adoption of, or engagement with RRI or RRI-like ideas. In the European Union, at least for firms that received funding from public research councils, requirements to engage with RRI frameworks such as RRI Keys or AREA played of course a central role. In the interviews with industry innovators from other world parts, several types of external drivers could be identified. These included, policy drivers, such as policies and regulation that promoted diversity and gender equality, environmental policies and standards, or employment rights. Other types of external drivers were the UN SDGs, as well as industry specific regulations and standards such as safety protocols for GMOs or nuclear safety analysis. Internal drivers included internalized value convictions and moral norms, which instill reflection on innovation processes, at least in some respondents. Motivations for change and more responsible and sustainable innovation came also from an awareness of societal and environmental problems and the experience of poverty, deprivation and lack of opportunities and life chances in local communities, especially in lower income countries.

Challenges to the adoption of RRI-like practices in industry

While, in contrast to academic researchers, firms do not have to comply with the rules and responsibility expectations of public funding bodies, they are exposed to other demands, such as pressure to deliver new, profitable innovations, the need for ongoing cash-flows, expectations from customers, and stresses arising from dependency on banks and private financiers. Our data show, that these factors can RRI to a low priority issue, especially if it is not certain that the adoption of RRI practices leads to economic gains or other benefits. Some respondents pointed out, that there is a clear danger that financial pressure in companies, and sometimes perhaps outright greed, can result in firms cutting corners on the implementation of safety measures and other RRI aspects.

Several other challenges to the adoption of RRI-like practices emerged. These included a tension between demands for open data and open science and the need for secrecy in industry innovation. These concerns went beyond proprietary issues and IPR. Some respondents were concerned, for example, that open data could be used selectively, which make a company look bad and cause reputational damage. Others feared that unrestricted access to research data could, at least with specific types of data, lead to forms of dual use or the creation of inventions that could harm societies and the environment.

Various challenges emerged from differences in the broader political and socio-economic contexts in which private sector innovation takes place. The data provided a variety of insights of how these contexts can create practical problems and influence the ways in which RRI or RRI-like ideas are understood and implemented. A first challenges concerned problems with government regulations, such as lack of effective regulation, lack of implementation or the absence of an effective infrastructure or political motivation, through which implementation of RRI (or similar) policies can be encouraged and enforced. A second

challenge relates to the prevalence of corruption in some countries. Corruption allows companies, at least if they wish so, to effectively sideline regulatory and legal requirements. This makes the consistent implementation of ethical and regulatory standards, as well as other RRI components, often difficult or impossible to achieve. A more general challenge is lack of resources to support and create the capacity for the development and implementation of RRI-like ideas. If governments do not provide sufficient resources, for example to facilitate a transition to renewable energies or to subsidize other, more sustainable forms of production, RRI-like practices are hard to realize.

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Appendix A: Codebook

Aggregate Codes	Meaning	Code Category	Meaning
1. Understandings of RRI in industry	This category examines how industry stakeholders understand RRI and RRI-related practices, and whether they think that RRI is feasible for industry innovation.	Definitions of responsibility	Situated understandings of responsibility in corporate innovation processes.
		Irresponsible innovation	Understandings and examples of problematic or irresponsible forms of private sector innovation.
		RRI as procedure	Understandings of the steps and stages through which RRI is/can be applied in industry.
		Upstream RRI	Perceptions and forms of RRI at the level of upstream innovation.
		Downstream RRI	Perceptions and forms of RRI at the level of downstream innovation.
		RRI in business models	Understandings of the role of RRI ideas in business models
		RRI as purpose and aspiration	Perceptions of RRI as an unrealised and possibly unrealisable ideal for industry innovation.
		Feasibility of RRI	Understandings of the feasibility of (public sector) RRI in corporate contexts.
		Alternatives to RRI	Perceptions of alternatives to RRI in industry innovation.
		Whose responsibility to adopt RRI	Understandings of whose responsibility it is to promote and adopt RRI in corporate innovation.
		Perspectives on RRI in industry – from outside industry	Perceptions of RRI in industry – as put forward by non-industry stakeholders (e.g. NGOs, etc)
		Disadvantages of RRI	Understandings of the problems and disadvantages that RRI can cause in corporations.
		2. Role and value of RRI in industry	This category seeks to explore perceptions of the role and value of RRI in private sector innovation contexts.
Motivations to use RRI	Perceptions of the motivations to promote or adopt RRI in private sector innovation.		
RRI and SDGs	Perceptions of the role of RRI in realising sustainable development goals (SDGs)		
Managing stakeholder relationships	RRI as a means to manage and improve relations with		

			stakeholders, including customers
		Understand perceptions of customers	RRI as a form of marketing research, that generates knowledge about consumers.
		Address societal concerns	RRI as a means to identify and address societal concerns.
		Understanding environmental impacts	RRI as a means to identify and address environmental issues.
		Preventing adverse effects	RRI as a means to identify and prevent adverse effects of technoscientific innovation.
		Prevent dual use and misuse	RRI as a means to identify and prevent dual use or misuse of technoscientific innovations.
		RRI as ethics washing	RRI as a means of public image management and to legitimize controversial practices or technology applications.
3. Dimensions and described practices of RRI in industry contexts	Seeks to understand the different dimensions and practices of RRI in private sector innovation, and how, whether and in which ways these relate to the AREA, AIRR and RRI Keys frameworks. Central aims here are (i) to understand how RRI-related ideas are operationalised and put into practice, and (ii) to identify differences or “gaps” between how RRI has been defined in the public research sector in the UK and EU, and the ways in which ideas of responsibility and responsible innovation are conceptualised in industry settings and different world regions.	Anticipation	Practices associated with anticipation and foresight in industry innovation.
		Reflectivity	Practices associated with reflectivity in industry innovation.
		Public engagement	Practices associated with public engagement and stakeholder deliberation in industry.
		Inclusion in industry innovation	Practices associated with the promotion of inclusion and equal opportunities in industry.
		Gender	Perceptions of gender dimensions in innovation and practices to address gender inequalities.
		Diversity	Perceptions of issues related to diversity in innovation and practices to promote diversity.
		Ethics	Practices associated with ethics, ethicality and ethics management in industry.
		Science communication and public outreach	Practices associated with science communication and outreach in industry
		RRI training	Opinions, ideas and practices associated with RRI training in private sector contexts.
		Access to new innovations or products	Practices and ideas related to the promotion of broad access to new products and services.
		Innovation governance	RRI-related practices that inform the governance of innovation processes in industry.

		Open access and data sharing	Practices and ideas related to the promotion of open access and data sharing.
		Transparency	Practices and ideas related to the promotion and feasibility of transparency in industry.
4. Drivers for RRI engagement	This seeks to identify the policy drivers for RRI adoption in industry innovation, and how this differs across countries, political systems and inequalities in wealth and scientific resources.	National policies	The role and effects of national policies in driving the adoption of RRI in private sector innovation.
		International policies	The role and effects of international policies in driving RRI adoption in private sector innovation.
		Institutional policies	The role and effects of institutional policies in driving RRI adoption in industry.
		Pressure to adhere to international standards	The role and effects of international standards in driving RRI adoption in private sector innovation.
		Participation in International collaborations	The role and effects of international collaborations in driving RRI adoption of RRI in firms.
		Access to markets in multiple countries	The role and effects of aspirations to access multiple markets in driving RRI adoption in firms.
		Corporate self-governance	Lack of policy or regulatory vacuum – triggering forms of corporate self-governance
		Public debate	Public debate as a driver for government or institutional policies that promote RRI-related ideas.
5. Challenges to RRI adoption in industry	This category seeks to identify and understand some of the central challenges to the adoption of RRI ideas and policies in industrial innovation contexts	Limitations of public sector RRI in industry	Tensions that arise between public sector RRI and the characteristics & needs of industry innovation.
		Costs of RRI	The financial aspects of RRI adoption, and whether RRI is seen as profitable and worthwhile.
		Lack of understanding of RRI	Lack of understanding among corporate staff of what RRI is, why it is of value.
		Lack of knowledge on how to do RRI	Lack of understanding among corporate staff on how to apply RRI ideas in industry settings.
		Uncertainties about who should do RRI	Uncertainties about who is responsible to promote, finance and implement RRI.

		Value of RRI for corporations not clear	Lack of understanding of the potential value and benefits of RRI adoption in corporate settings.
		Need for secrecy in industry innovation	Tensions between demands for open access and transparency and the need for secrecy in firms.
		Economic incentives override RRI	Economic incentives and priorities weigh stronger than a commitment to ethics and RRI.
		Insufficient support from management	RRI adoption is insufficiently supported at the higher management level in firms.
		Challenges to operationalise and implement RRI	Corporate staff find it difficult to operationalise and implement RRI ideas in industry innovation.
		Insufficient support from the government	Challenges arising from insufficient support to promote RRI ideas by national (or regional) government administrations.
6. Challenges to RRI adoption in a diverse global environment	This category seeks to understand key challenges to the adoption of RRI in industry in a diverse global landscape, that is characterised by cultural, social and political heterogeneity, as well as unequal distribution of wealth, resources, social security and health care.	Governments do not support RRI	Lack of support and/or different priorities results in insufficient government support for RRI adoption.
		Economic priorities outweigh concern with RRI	Economic priorities and demands for rapid development are more important than a systematic concern with ethics and RRI.
		RRI as undermining competitiveness	RRI and ethics are seen as hindering effective innovation and undermining (international or interfirm) competitiveness.
		Secretive innovation	Challenges for the adoption of RRI due to the secretive nature of military innovation.
		Lack of infrastructures and resources	Lack of financial resources as well as regulatory infrastructures prevent effective adoption of RRI.
		Different political systems	Non-democratic contexts prevent RRI and public dialogue.
		Diverse understandings of ethics & responsibility	Challenges to RRI adoption that arise from cultural and social heterogeneity.
		Lack of trust	Challenges to RRI adoption that arise from a lack of trust in government, science, corporations or other institutions or stakeholders

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